

**BLDE (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) SHRI BM PATIL MEDICAL
COLLEGE AND RESEARCH CENTRE VIJAYAPURA, KARNATAKA.**

TITLE OF THE TOPIC

**“A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COBLATION VS CONVENTIONAL
TONSILLECTOMY”**

**DR RADHIKA R KRISHNAN
POSTGRADUATE IN OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY**

PROFORMA FOR REGISTRATION OF SUBJECT FOR DISSERTATION

UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF

DR. H.T.LATHADEVI

MS ENT, Ph D

PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

BLDE(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY),

**SHRI BM PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH
CENTRE, KARNATAKA**

BLDE DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY, VIJAYAPURA, KARNATAKA

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COBLATION VS CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY**” is a bonafide and genuine research work carried out by me under the guidance of **Dr. H.T.LATHADEVI**, Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology at B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be university), Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka

Date:

Signature of the Candidate

Place: Vijayapura, Karnataka

DR. RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN

Post Graduate student,

Department of Otorhinolaryngology

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical

College, Hospital & Research Centre,

Vijayapura, Karnataka.

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.

CERTIFICATE BY THE GUIDE

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COBLATION VS CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr.RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN** in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of M.S. in Otorhinolaryngology.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura, Karnataka.

H.T. Lathadevi

Signature of the Guide

Dr. H.T.LATHADEVI M.S

Professor,

Department of Otorhinolaryngology,

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B.M. Patil

Medical College, Hospital & Research

Centre, Vijayapura.

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA

ENDORSEMENT BY HEAD OF DEPARTMENT AND PRINCIPAL

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COBLATION VS CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY” is a bonafide research work done by **Dr.RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN** under the guidance of **DR.H.T.LATHADEVI**, Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology at BLDE (Deemed to be university), Shri.B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka.

Seal & Signature of HOD

Dr. R.N.KARADI M.S.,

Professor and Head of Department,

Otorhinolaryngology,

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B.M. Patil

Medical College, Hospital &

Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura.

Dr. ARAVIND.V. PATIL M.S.,

Principal & Dean,

Faculty of Medicine,

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B.M. Patil

Medical College, Hospital &

Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Date:

Place: Vijayapura.

Seal & Signature of Principal

B.L.D.E. (Deemed to be University)
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH
CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.

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Date:

Place: Vijayapura, Karnataka

Signature of the Candidate

DR.RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN M.B.B.S.

Post Graduate student,

Department of Otorhinolaryngology

B.L.D.E. (DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical

College, Hospital & Research Centre,

Vijayapura, Karnataka

©BLDE (Deemed to be University), Karnataka

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It is with glorious veneration and intense gratitude, I would like to thank my esteemed teacher and guide **Dr.H.T.LATHADEVI**, Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU)'s Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura who was ever encouraging in her approach while helping me through my postgraduate course. She was always supportive and allowed me to work and develop at my own pace, guiding wherever necessary. Without her guidance and support, it would have been impossible to complete this dissertation.

I am immensely thankful to **Dr.ARAVIND.V.PATIL**, Principal, BLDE (DU) Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, for allowing me to do this work, to use facilities in this institution and for his encouragement and support throughout my postgraduate course.

I am grateful to **Dr. R.N.KARADI**, Professor and Head of Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery, BLDE (DU) Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura. I am thankful for their help and advice during my postgraduate course.

I express my sincere gratitude to Assitant professors , **Dr. Shashi Kumar, Dr Manali and Dr. Shivashankar Ajur** , Senior Residents , **Dr.Sunita Y, Dr. Sharanabassu, Dr Anuja Panicker** Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, for their concern, suggestions and constructive encouragement.

I am immensely thankful to my Postgraduate colleagues and friends, **Dr. Mohan Raaj , Dr. Justin , Dr. Surekha , Dr.Ashwini patil, Dr.Sushma , Dr.Sagarika , Dr. Reshma , Dr. Adishree , Dr.Nivedha,Dr.Meghana,Dr.Amit,Dr.Neelima,Dr.Manisha** and **Dr.Tomin** for their immense help and support during my postgraduate course. I thank them from my heart.

I am eternally grateful to my beloved family; my parents **Mr.P.Radhakrishnan** and **Mrs. Sobhanamma G** , my husband **Mr. Prashant V.S** and my sister **Mrs.Gopika.Krishnan** who have nurtured me and supported me in all my endeavours, without their love and innumerable sacrifices, I would not be the person I am today.

I would like to thank, Audiologists **Ms.Rakshita** and **Ms.Sangeetha**

Statisticians **Mrs. Vijaya Sorganvi**, Asst. Librarian for their support during my post graduate course. I am filled with gratitude to all my study subjects whose co-operation has contributed to this study.

Finally, I bow my head in a silent acknowledgement of all that **The Lord Almighty** has blessed me with.

Date:

DR. RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN

Place: Vijayapura, Karnataka

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

%	Percentage
POD	Post Operative Day
NBM	Nil by mouth
OT	Operation theatre
ppw	Posterior pharyngeal wall
RFA	Radiofrequency ablation
VAS	Visual Analogue Scale
Ig s	Immunoglobulins
IJV	Internal jugular vein
GA	General anaesthesia
aPTT	Activated partial thromboplastin time
PT	Prothrombin time
OSA	Obstructive sleep apnoea
CAA	Cold dissection adenotonsillectomy
CDA	Coblation assisted adenotonsillectomy

ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION –NEED TO STUDY

Tonsils affected by infectious diseases are common in otorhinolaryngological practice, whether in adults or children. One of the most common surgical procedures done by otorhinolaryngologists is tonsillectomy.¹Palatine tonsils are collections of lymphoid tissue situated in the oropharynx within the tonsillar fossa.² Tonsils play an important role in the immunological defence mechanism of the body. Secretory IgA (antibody secretions) will help in the mucosal defense mechanism. Their protective mechanism sometimes fails and becomes the seat of infection, causing sore throat, fever, and other complications due to unknown etiology that require removal of the diseased tonsils.²Otorhinolaryngologist are keen to know about the intraoperative and postoperative bleeding complications caused by tonsillectomy, despite being the most standard and simplest surgery as it may lead to shock and death. The risk of hemorrhage is very high in tonsillectomy because of the rich blood supply. Coblation tonsillectomy was introduced in 2001 and many studies show its efficacy regarding less complications.

Hence, this study mainly aims at comparing coblation and conventional tonsillectomy.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

This study is done to compare the following factors between coblation and conventional tonsillectomy like:

1. Time taken for surgery
2. Intraoperative & postoperative blood loss
3. Postoperative pain
4. Time required to return to normal diet and activity
5. Incidence of reactionary & secondary hemorrhage

METHODOLOGY

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

1. Patients undergoing tonsillectomy in Department of Otorhinolaryngology , BLDE (Deemed to be University) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College and Research Center, Vijayapura.

2. The outpatient department will screen each case and will undergo a general physical examination, local ENT examination, and laboratory and radiological examination. Fitness for surgery will be taken.

3. The data will be collected in the form of clinical examination, mode of surgery, time taken for surgery, intraoperative & postoperative blood loss, postoperative pain, time required to return to normal diet and activity and incidence of reactionary & secondary hemorrhage.

4. Postoperative outcomes will be obtained via a questionnaire administered to the patient or caregiver.

5. Patients will be followed up postoperatively for five days with antibiotics and for ten days to observe for hemorrhage/pain. Postoperative bleeding from the tonsillar fossa will be assessed by the type of procedure that the patient will undergo the day on which it occurred and the measures that will be taken to stop it. Postoperatively, patients are followed till 10th day.

RESULTS

This study compared 55 coblation tonsillectomies and 55 conventional tonsillectomies in 110 patients. This study showed that the maximum number of patients were in the age group of 10-19 years, and the least were in the age group above 40 years. The total number of female patients in both coblation and conventional tonsillectomy was 66(60%), and male patients were 44(40.0%). Coblation and conventional had equal numbers of female 33(60%) and male 22(40%) patients. Females are more in our study, with an equal number of both sexes in each group. Conventional tonsillectomy took more time, (53.51±13.434)min, compared to coblation tonsillectomy, (29.64±7.352) min, which was significant with a P value < 0.0001. The mean intraoperative blood loss is less for coblation (51.45±12.521) ML and more for conventional (88.89±16.992) ML. It is statistically significant with a P value < 0.0001. The postoperative pain score is found to be more for conventional than coblation tonsillectomy. Postoperative pain score on POD 1, POD 5, and POD 10 for coblation is (6.80±1.2, 5.20±1.193, 1.02±1.269) and conventional is (8.25±1.158), (5.89±1.462), (3.31±1.597) respectively. It is statistically significant with a P value < 0.0001 for POD 1 and POD-10. POD -5 had p- value < 0.012. The time required to return to regular diet and activity is less for coblation (4.29±1.165) than conventional (8.05±1.682) tonsillectomy. It is statistically significant with a P value < 0.05.

CONCLUSION

The coblation tonsillectomy, compared to conventional tonsillectomy, is a better method as it significantly reduced the operative time, intraoperative blood loss and postoperative pain and the patient can return to normal diet and routine activities faster. The incidence of postoperative hemorrhage was not significant by either method.

Keywords: Tonsillectomy, Coblation, Conventional, Complication, Intraoperative, Postoperative, Hemorrhage.

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INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION –NEED TO STUDY

Tonsils affected by infectious diseases are common in otorhinolaryngological practice, whether in adults or children. One of the most common surgical procedures done by otorhinolaryngologists is tonsillectomy.¹

Palatine tonsils are collections of lymphoid tissue situated in the oropharynx within the tonsillar fossa.²

Tonsils play an important role in the immunological defence mechanism of the body. Secretory IgA (antibody secretions) will help in the mucosal defense mechanism. Their protective mechanism sometimes fails and becomes the seat of infection, causing sore throat, fever, and other complications due to unknown etiology that require removal of the diseased tonsils.²

Otorhinolaryngologist are keen to know about the complications like intraoperative and postoperative bleeding caused by tonsillectomy, despite being the most standard and simplest surgery as it may lead to shock and death.

The risk of hemorrhage is very high in tonsillectomy because of the rich blood supply.

There is significant morbidity following tonsillectomy. It incorporates perioperative and postoperative hemorrhage and pain. The child is prevented from returning to a regular diet, resulting in dehydration and prolonged hospital stay¹⁴ due to postoperative pain and difficulty in swallowing.

Patients after surgery may also experience difficulty in swallowing, throat and ear pain, nausea, vomiting, fever, dehydration, weight loss and airway obstruction.²

“Postoperative pain and bleeding are the two major postoperative complications caused by traditional tonsillectomy, as it leaves the wound open to heal by secondary intention. “There are various methods described in other literature for tonsillectomy, which include dissection, guillotine, cryosurgery, monopolar and bipolar diathermy dissection and laser surgery.”¹⁶

Superiority of one procedure over the other cannot be demonstrated. The techniques to decrease pain and bleeding are concentrated on by pioneers. Watchful waiting for recurrent tonsillitis has been reported to cost highly.³

Coblation tonsillectomy was initially introduced in 2001⁴, following which a significant number of articles were published to confirm its efficacy.

Coblation generates a substantially low thermal effect compared to electrocautery, estimated between 40 - 70°C⁵, with a subsequent presumption of diminished collateral thermal damage to surrounding tissues. While in electrocautery, which is used in conventional dissection tonsillectomy, it reaches up to 400 - 600°C.^{6,7}

Hence, this study mainly aims to compare coblation and conventional tonsillectomy.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

This study is done to compare the following factors between coblation and conventional tonsillectomy like:

- 1) Time taken for surgery
- 2) Intraoperative & postoperative blood loss
- 3) Postoperative pain
- 4) Time required to return to normal diet and activity
- 5) Incidence of reactionary & secondary haemorrhage

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HISTORY

“In the first century AD, Aulus Cornelius Celsus was the first to do tonsillectomy by finger dissection. Vinegar was used for preventing after-surgery bleeding .⁸”

“In the 6th Century AD, Aetius of Amidain introduced the Hook and Knife method. The tonsillotome was created by Philip Syng Physick. He was known as the “Father of American surgery.”⁸”

“The strangulation procedure was championed by Ambroise Pare(1564) and improved by Scultetus(1655), which allowed the placement of a thread around the tonsil and cutting off by strangulation.”

“By slowly developing acceptance, partial excision of tonsils became a possibility. Given the surgical bleeding restrictions and lack of anesthesia, many evolutions were made in instrumentation for grasping and excising the tonsil to make the method efficient.⁸”

“In 1828, Philip Sung Physick had modified a guillotine to use on tonsils, which was planned for uvulectomy by Norwegian laborer Canute of Thorbern and was modified by Benjamin Bell of Edinburgh after noticing the execution device invented by Dr.J.L.Guillotin in France.⁸”

“It became a model for similar instruments created by William Fahnestock(1832), Morrell Mackenzie(1880), Greenfield Sluder(1911),and Otto Oswald Popper(1929).⁹”

“Snares Pierce-Mueller Middledorpf(with galvanocautery) were also culminated and used for tonsillectomy.⁸”

“Joseph C. Beck devised a hybrid device that is a snare harboring a wire within a rigid ring.⁸”

“Towards the end of the 19th century, several advancements were made that caused markable changes in the execution of tonsillectomy.”

“To begin with, surgeons created superior illumination techniques for the head and neck, supplanting general surgeons as the primary specialists of tonsil surgery and using ligatures (Cohen) and galvanocautery(Dillinger) to improve postoperative hemostasis.⁸”

“Tonsillotomy was done using anesthetic agents like cocaine that act locally. However, general anesthesia was required to excise the tonsils completely. Extended methods to perform tonsillectomy more accurately and with less strain happened after Morton’s first portrayal 1846 of ether anaesthesia.⁸”

“In 1906, William Lincoln Ballenger did the complete removal of tonsils with the intact capsule. Complete tonsillectomy was demonstrated initially by George Ernest Waugh in 1909.⁸”

“From 1911-1917, 1000 tonsil surgeries were done by Crowe using Crowe Davis Mouth gag using the dissection method.⁸”

Chang, et al. 2004 performed a prospective random double-blind study that compared coblation tonsillectomy with electrocautery tonsillectomy.⁹ Wong-Baker FACES pain scale for postoperative pain was found to be better on each postoperative pain from day 1 to 6 in the coblation method. Similarly, patients who underwent coblation tonsillectomy returned to regular diet and activities by postoperative day 5.¹⁰

Stoker, et al. 2004 compared coblation with electrocautery adenotonsillectomy in this prospective single-blinded study. Their study showed no change in postoperative return to diet and normal activity, absence of pain or use of nonnarcotic pain medications between these two methods. Using the Wong-Baker FACES pain scale, narcotic pain medication was stopped for coblation patients. For coblation patients from each POD 1 -POD 6 was better with ($P < 0.005$). Similarly coblation patients resumed normal diet faster than electrocautery patients ($P < 0.005$) and returned to normal activities sooner as well by POD 5 ($P < 0.005$).¹¹

Mohammadreza Omrani, et al. 2012 in a prospective double-blind, randomized controlled trial of 47 patients who underwent coblation or the traditional method of tonsillectomy, was done. Coblation was considered to be safe and effective. Coblation reduced operative time, intraoperative blood loss, and postoperative pain and was associated with normal routines and activities.¹²

Shapiro, et al. March 2017 conducted a prospective, randomized, single-blind trial of pediatric patients aged 2 to 16 years undergoing adenotonsillectomy. Patients randomly underwent either CAA or CDA. Coblation tonsillectomy was compared to better intraoperative hemostasis and operative speed than the conventional method.

There was no significant difference in postoperative pain. The 20 adult patients who had undergone tonsillectomy each had one tonsil removed by coblation and the other by conventional method. The visual analogue scale recorded the subjective pain level daily for 10 postoperative days.¹³

K.Muthubabu, et al. 2018 compared coblation with conventional tonsillectomy based on age group, gender, duration of surgery, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative pain and postoperative blood loss. Coblation tonsillectomy was easy and safer in terms of intra-operative blood loss and postoperative pain. The cost factor is the only disadvantage, and it provides a bloodless field with minimal tissue damage. The coblation method took more operative time than the dissection method. The intraoperative blood loss was significantly less in the coblation tonsillectomy than in the dissection method. The postoperative pain score was significantly lower for coblation than the conventional method that helps the patient to return to regular diet and activity.¹⁴

Mostafa El-Taher, et al. 2019 in a double-blinded, randomized controlled trial, compared coblation versus conventional tonsillectomy in view of operative time, operative blood loss, the incidence of primary and secondary postoperative hemorrhage and time required to return to normal activity and diet. The study included 1004 patients. Coblation tonsillectomy is comparatively better than the dissection method, with less operative time, reduced intraoperative blood loss, and early return to daily activities and normal diet. Coblation tonsillectomy was associated with a higher incidence of secondary hemorrhage.¹⁵

Vivek Sasindran, et al. 2019 compared dissection and coblation tonsillectomy based on the time taken for surgery, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative pain and the time required to return to normal diet and activity. There was a significant

difference in intraoperative time and blood loss for coblation. The average postoperative pain score following 6 hours of surgery was 7.6 for coblation and 8.5 for cold dissection. The time to return to normal diet among coblation was 6.4 days, and dissection was 7.0 days. Coblation tonsillectomy significantly reduced the operative time, intraoperative blood loss, and postoperative pain, and the patient returned to normal diet and activity with a higher cost.¹⁶

Shifa Vyas, et al. 2019 compared operative time, intraoperative bleeding, and postoperative pain between coblation and dissection tonsillectomy. Coblation tonsillectomy requires more operative time, which can be reduced with further experience. The patients who had undergone coblation tonsillectomy had fewer postoperative complications. The operative time required to perform the procedure can be reduced with further experience.¹⁷

Neha Mihir Karathia, et al. 2020 compared the time spent on surgery, intraoperative blood loss, degree of slough formation, and postoperative pain as complications between coblation and conventional tonsillectomy. The coblation procedure reduced the intraoperative time, intraoperative blood loss, less charring of tissues and damage to surrounding structures, and postoperative pain after 24 hours, which is less in coblation than the dissection method. The patients who had undergone coblation tonsillectomy had more slough formation than the dissection method.¹⁸

Zhengcai Lou, et al. 2022 compared intraoperative blood loss, postoperative pain, postoperative bleeding, and cost factor of extracapsular tonsillectomy between coblation and monopolar electrocautery in children.¹⁹ Both procedures had similar postoperative pain scores except on postoperative days 1 and 2. Postoperative pain

scores, except on postoperative days 1 and 2, were identical for both coblation and novel monopolar electrocautery extracapsular tonsillectomy. On the contrary, the monopolar technique causes less operative time and decreased secondary PTH and cost compared to coblation.¹⁹

Kanchan Chaudhary, et al. 2023 compared coblation vs. conventional tonsillectomy in a prospective study using postoperative pain, bleeding, fever, pharyngitis, injury of adjacent structure & cautery burn. The average intraoperative blood loss for conventional tonsillectomy was 44.2 ml, and coblation was 44.2 ml. For coblation-assisted tonsillectomy cautery burn, injury to adjacent structures and postoperative pain score were significantly decreased. The peri or postoperative blood loss, postoperative pain, injury to adjacent structures and cautery burns are reduced by using coblation.²⁰

ANATOMY

EMBRYOLOGY

During the fifth month of development, the Waldeyer ring is a ring of lymphoid tissue that encircles the developing respiratory and digestive tract.(Image 1)

The ring comprises of (from superior to inferior):

- 1) Pharyngeal tonsils called the Adenoids in the upper midline of the nasopharynx) and tubal tonsils (around the eustachian tube opening)
- 2) Laterally, on either side of the oropharynx, the Palatine tonsils
- 3) Inferiorly in the hypopharynx and posterior one-third of the tongue, the Lingual tonsils.

Scattered lymphoid follicles throughout the pharynx and the lateral pharyngeal bands are also included in this group.

IMAGE 1:WALDEYER'S TONSILLAR RING

“The interaction of mesenchymal, lymphoid and epithelial cells results in the formation of lymphoid structures.⁸ The tonsillar crypts are formed when a wedge of endodermal epithelial cells surrounds the mesoderm.²¹”

“During the fourth fetal month, the crypts develop into the epithelial connective tissue and are invaded by lymphoid tissue. The first primary follicles are formed during the fifth month. By the seventh month, the pharyngeal adenoid tissue will be fully formed.”

“During the third fetal month, the second pharyngeal pouch ventral portion develops into the palatine tonsils^{8,21}”

“During the fourth month, canalization occurs via programmed cell death around the pharyngeal wall mesenchyme endodermal epithelial buds.²¹”

“In the third trimester, lymphoid follicles are organised. Growth continues after birth. Supra tonsillar fossa is a persistent depression at the superior pole of the tonsil, the only remnant of the second pouch.²² Tubal tonsils develop from 1st pharyngeal pouch.”The lingual tonsils develop in association with the posterior two-thirds of the tongue.²²”

“The dorsal mesenchyme extension in the developing soft palate from the second and third branchial arches forms the tonsillar pillars In the 14th week, mononuclear cells invade the mesenchyme of the tonsillar fossa mucosa. The mesenchymal cells solidify and form the tonsillar lymphoid tissue.”

In the 16th week, nodular structures were seen over tissue primordium. At 6th month of age, primary follicles are formed.

In 20 th week, mesenchyme forms the internal connective tissue and capsule of the tonsils.

Until birth, germinal centers that function are absent, and they become established after birth.

PALATINE TONSILS ANATOMY

Image 2:Tonsil Disease - Dearborn ENT - Livonia – Otolaryngology:Online

IMAGE 2: PALATINE TONSILS

“Two oval lymphoid tissues within the tonsillar fossa are embedded between the anterior(palatoglossal) and posterior(palatopharyngeal) tonsillar pillars. At birth, the palatine tonsils weigh approximately 0.75 -0.34 gm and are anteroposteriorly 5mm in diameter and 3.5 mm in vertical diameter. ²³(Image 2)”

“The vertical diameter of the palatine tonsils grows faster than the anterioposterior diameter, causing their descent within the fossa during childhood. The palatine tonsils are covered with pharyngobasilar capsule fascia in contrast to other oronasal lymphoid tissues.”

“The capsule is separated from the underlying musculature by free connective tissue.

Pus can collect here and cause peritonsillar abscess.²⁴

Surfaces and Poles:

“A tonsil has two surfaces- The lateral surface and the medial surface. Two poles- upper and lower. The oropharynx epithelium is continuous with the epithelium of the tonsillar surface. The surface of the epithelium has tube-like invaginations called tonsillar crypts.”

Medial surface-

“Non-keratinising stratified squamous epithelium covers the medial surface of tonsils. The tonsillar substance is plunged by epithelium in the form of crypts. Tonsillar crypt openings can be seen. The medial surface faces the cavity of the oropharynx and is free. Crypta magna is situated near the upper part of the tonsil and is more prominent and deeper than the other crypts. It represents the ventral portion of the second pharyngeal pouch. Within the substance of the tonsils, secondary crypts arise from the primary crypts. Contraction of the palatopharyngeus muscle in this area moves the tonsils medially and towards the buccal cavity while swallowing.”

Lateral surface:

“A well-defined fibrous capsule is seen over the lateral surface of the tonsils. During tonsillectomy, loose areolar tissue between the capsule and bed of the tonsil makes it easy to dissect the tonsil in the plane. It is the site for the collection of pus in case of peritonsillar abscess. Some strands of palatoglossus and palatopharyngeus muscles are attached to the tonsil capsule.”

Posterior pillar

“It is formed by the palatopharyngeus muscle, which originates from the palatine aponeurosis and hard palate and is inserted into the soft palate.”

Anterior pillar

“It is formed by palatoglossal muscle. It originates from the inferior surface of the tongue, inserts within palatal aponeurosis, and forms an arch with palatopharyngeus.”

Supratonsillar fossa:

It is a semi-lunar fold that runs between the anterior and posterior pillars on the medial surface of the tonsillar upper pole. This enclosed space is known as the supratonsillar fossa. Carcinoma frequently occurs in the tonsillolingual sulcus, which divides the tonsil from the tongue.

Tonsillar Crypts:

“On the tonsil’s medial surface, the non keratinizing stratified squamous epithelium dips into the tonsillar mass to form crypts^{24,25,26,27}. Crypt openings are seen on the tonsil’s medial surface. Secondary crypts emerge from the primary crypts found in the tonsil substance.”

“Upon applying pressure to the crypts during infection, cheesy material made of epithelial cells, bacteria and food debris can be forced out of the cavities over the anterior tonsillar pillar.”

The styloid process:

“When enlarged, the styloid process can be felt intraorally in the tonsillar fossa’s lower region. Following tonsillectomy, the styloid process and the glossopharyngeal nerve are assessed through the tonsillar bed. During childhood, compared to the

anteroposterior diameter, the palatine tonsils' vertical diameter grows more quickly, causing the palatine tonsils to descend within their fossa.”

The Tonsillar Bed:

Unlike other oronasal lymphoid tissues, the palatine tonsils are covered with a pharyngobasilar capsule. Along the lateral surface of the tonsillar bed musculature, the styloid process and the glossopharyngeal nerve descend vertically.

The tonsillar bed comprises the structures - Capsule, pharyngobasilar fascia, buccopharyngeal fascia, superior constrictor muscle, facial artery, glossopharyngeal nerve, loose areolar tissue containing para tonsillar vein, medial pterygoid muscle, submandibular salivary gland and styloglossus muscle.

The “parapharyngeal space” is entered through the tonsillar bed and superior constrictor muscle when a penetrating injury is directed posterolaterally into the oropharynx. The internal jugular vein, internal carotid artery, sympathetic trunk, and the nerves connected to the carotid sheath at this location (CN X, XI, and XII) are among the structures in this area that are susceptible to damage.(Image 3)

IMAGE 3: TONSILLAR BED STRUCTURES

ARTERIAL BLOOD SUPPLY

- 1) Tonsillar artery, which is a branch of the facial artery.
- 2) Descending palatine branch of the maxillary artery
- 3) Lingual artery through its dorsal lingual branches.
- 4) Ascending palatine branch of facial artery
- 5) Ascending pharyngeal vessels from external carotid artery

In refractory bleeding following tonsillectomy, the ascending pharyngeal, facial, lingual, and maxillary arteries— all external carotid artery branches— might require ligation. The internal carotid artery is situated roughly 2.5 cm posterolateral to the tonsil, which is anatomically significant to note for surgical purposes.²¹(Image 4)

IMAGE 4:ARTERIAL BLOOD SUPPLY OF TONSIL

VENOUS DRAINAGE

The paratonsillar vein (external palatine) drains the Tonsils. The vessels pierce the superior constrictor and drain into the IJV via the facial vein or pharyngeal plexus.

LYMPHATIC DRAINAGE

The afferent lymphatics are absent in palatine tonsils. Instead, efferent lymphatics are formed by lymphatic plexuses that surround each follicle and pass toward the hemicapsule. They directly drain into the upper deep cervical lymph nodes (mainly the jugulodigastric nodes) after piercing through the buccopharyngeal fascia or indirectly into the retropharyngeal lymph nodes. Typical enlargement of the jugulodigastric nodes is seen in tonsillitis. They will be palpable superficially 1 to 2 cm below the angle of the mandible over the sternocleidomastoid muscle's anterior border. They can present as common neck swellings.

NERVE SUPPLY

Lesser palatine branches from the sphenopalatine ganglion of the maxillary division of the trigeminal nerve & Glossopharyngeal nerve (CN IX) are the two sensory innervations of the tonsils. Along with glossopharyngeal nerve tonsillar branches, the maxillary nerve forms the circulus tonsillaris plexus around the tonsils. Oropharyngeal isthmus and soft palate have innervations from this plexus. The pediatric patient may experience referred otalgia following tonsillectomy because the glossopharyngeal nerve supplies the medial wall of the tympanic membrane and the middle ear cavity. Infection, postoperative inflammation of the tonsils and tonsillar fossa and malignancy can cause referred otalgia.

HISTOLOGY

The non-keratinized stratified squamous epithelium covers the palatine tonsils. This epithelium merges with the mesenchymal structures as it infiltrates the crypts. There are 10–20 crypts in every tonsil. The crypts pierce the surface and descend to different levels. The tonsil is completely pierced to get to the fibrous capsule. The palatine tonsils grow after birth and remain active until age fifteen.²² After puberty, tonsillar tissue involutes, and more fibrosis manifests. The lingual tonsils grow at the base of the tongue later than the other oronasal tonsils. Long into adulthood, lingual tonsils continue to exist. Stratified squamous epithelium of the palatine tonsils infiltrates the crypts and combines with the mesenchymal structures.(Image 5)

IMAGE 5:HISTOPATHOLOGICAL APPEARANCE OF TONSIL²⁸

FUNCTION OF TONSIL

The tonsils actively synthesize IgG, IgM, and IgA, examples of humoral immunoglobulins. They are immunologically related to the human gut-associated lymphoid system and produce lymphocytes in the entire sequence of lymphopoiesis. The tonsils are thought to contribute to host immunity against pathogens because they are the first lymphoid aggregates to come into contact with pathogens that enter the body through the gastrointestinal and upper respiratory tracts.²⁹ Soon after birth, the immune system is stimulated, and the tonsils also produce lymphocytes. They are immunologically associated with the gut-associated lymphoid system in humans. Around two weeks of age, terminally differentiated plasma cells are visible. Secondary follicles develop as a result of this. The proliferation of these germinal centers can explain the rapid tonsillar growth observed in pediatrics. Expected tonsillar hypertrophy results from the tonsils continuing to enlarge rather than penetrating nearby tissue.²⁹

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF TONSILS

ACUTE TONSILLITIS

DEFINITION:

“An acute inflammatory condition of the tonsils affects the tonsillar mucosa, crypts, follicles, and parenchymal tissue. They can be affected by upper respiratory tract infection following viral etiology or primary infection of the tonsils. It can also occur as a localised infection and is not associated with URTI or can occur as part of a generalised systemic infection like infectious mononucleosis. The causative organism usually is GABHS(Group A beta-haemolytic streptococcus pyogenes).^{30,31”}

The other organisms that can cause infection are:

- 1) Streptococcus pneumonia
- 2) Haemophilus influenza
- 3) Staphylococcus

“The adenovirus, influenza, mycoplasma, parainfluenza, EBV and enterovirus account for 90% of these infections.^{32”}

“Acute tonsillar infection presents with a sore throat, pyrexia, cervical lymphadenopathy(jugulodigastric lymph nodes are tender and enlarged), muffled voice, excessive secretions, and general discomfort and fatigue. There is erythema and edema with exudates of the pharyngeal and tonsillar mucosa, although petechiae are more typical of viral illness. “

“Treatment varies with etiology; throat culture is indicated for treatable bacterial causes. Viral tonsillitis requires no specific treatment.”

“Tonsillitis causes by either bacterial or viral etiology tend to recover faster without treatment.³³ Along with antibiotics, oral or intramuscular corticosteroids cause faster resolution of pain.^{34,35} Symptomatic management of acute tonsillitis using adequate

hydration and painkillers is done till the symptoms subside. The risk of sequelae and illness span will be reduced by using antibiotics.²⁵ In patients with no signs of improvement within 48-72 hours, benzyl-penicillin, antibiotic being the drug of choice, is started. In case of severe illness, antibiotics are started early. Evidence suggests that in severe cases of sore throats, corticosteroids provide symptomatic relief from pain along with antibiotics.²⁶(Image 6)”

1)Acute catarrhal/superficial tonsillitis:

General infection of the oropharyngeal mucosa causes enlarged tonsils. It is mainly seen in viral etiology.

2)Acute follicular tonsillitis:

Multiple yellowish-whitish spots will be seen on the inflamed tonsillar surface due to exudative inflammatory collection in the tonsillar crypts.

3) Acute membranous tonsillitis:

The tonsillar surface may form a membrane from the coalescing of exudates in crypts.

4)Acute parenchymatous tonsillitis:

Due to hyperplasia of the lymphoid follicles of the parenchyma of the tonsil, the whole tonsil is uniformly enlarged and congested.

IMAGE 6:ACUTE TONSILLITIS³⁶

GRADING OF TONSILS

Tonsils are classified into grading system based on size of tonsil.³⁷(Table 1,Image 8,Table 2)

“BRODSKY GRADING SCALE/AAOHNS GRADATION OF TONSILLAR ENLARGEMENT³⁷”		
GRADE	DEFINITION	DESCRIPTION
“0 ³⁷ ”	“ NOT VISIBLE ³⁷ ”	“TONSILS DON’T REACH THE TONSILLAR PILLARS/SURGICALLY REMOVED ³⁷ ”
“1+ ³⁷ ”	“LESS THAN 25% ³⁷ ”	“TONSILS FILL LESS THAN 25% OF THE TRANSVERSE OROPHARYNGEAL SPACE MEASURED BETWEEN ANTERIOR PILLARS ³⁷ ”
“2+ ³⁷ ”	“25%-49% ³⁷ ”	“TONSILS FILL LESS THAN 50% OF TRANSVERSE OROPHARYNGEAL SPACE ³⁷ ”
“3+ ³⁷ ”	“50%-74% ³⁷ ”	“TONSILS FILL LESS THAN 75% OF TRANSVERSE OROPHARYNGEAL SPACE ³⁷ ”
“4+ ³⁷ ”	“75% OR MORE ³⁷ ”	“TONSILS FILL MORE THAN 75% OF TRANSVERSE OROPHARYNGEAL SPACE ³⁷ ”

TABLE 1: BRODSKY GRADING SCALE/AAOHNS GRADATION OF TONSILLAR ENLARGEMENT³⁷

**IMAGE 7: BRODSKY GRADING SCALE/AAOHNS
GRADATION OF TONSILLAR ENLARGEMENT³⁷**

FRIEDMAN GRADES OF TONSILLAR HYPERTROPHY³⁷	
GRADE 0	NO TONSILS SEEN/SURGICALLY REMOVED
GRADE 1	WITHIN TONSILLAR FOSSA
GRADE 2	VISIBLE BEYOND ANTERIOR PILLARS
GRADE 3	EXTEND 3/4 TH WAY TO MIDLINE
GRADE 4	COMPLETELY OBSTRUCTING AIRWAY (KISSING TONSIL)

TABLE 2 : FRIEDMAN GRADES OF TONSILLAR HYPERTROPHY³⁷

RECURRENT TONSILLITIS

Recurrent acute tonsillitis attacks may gradually settle or continue for several years. There is no evidence of any benefit from long-term antibiotics for this condition.

CHRONIC TONSILLITIS:

Occurs when recurrent attacks of acute tonsillitis are not adequately treated. There will be the development of abscesses within lymphoid follicles that get walled off by fibrous tissues.

There are three types :

1) Chronic follicular tonsillitis

Is seen commonly in adults where the tonsillar follicles are inflamed and swollen, and the crypts contain exudative material.

2) Chronic parenchymatous tonsillitis

Seen commonly in children due to recurrent acute attacks, hyperplasia of lymphoid follicles resulting in uniform tonsil enlargement.

3) Chronic fibrotic tonsillitis

The tonsils get atrophied and are small in size. There will be associated halitosis, fetor, hawking sensation or obstructive sleep apnoea. Systemic effects like fatigue, fever and loss of appetite may be evident due to reduced resistance.

The tongue might be dry and coated due to mouth breathing and poor food intake.

The 4 cardinal signs are:

1) Anterior tonsillar pillars are congested

2) Persistent enlarged jugulodigastric lymph nodes

3) Irwin Moore sign-On applying pressure over the anterior tonsillar pillars, pus pours out of crypts.

4) Tonsils are enlarged or atrophic.

COMPLICATIONS OF TONSILLITIS

- 1) Chronic tonsillitis with recurrent attacks,
- 2) Ascending infection leading to eustachian tube dysfunction, acute otitis media, otitis media with effusion,
- 3) Peritonsillar abscess, parapharyngeal abscess, retropharyngeal abscess.
- 4) Obstructive symptoms such as sleep apnoea.
- 5) Internal jugular vein thrombosis
- 6) Tonsillar cyst
- 7) Tonsilloliths
- 8) Voice change can occur due to restriction of movement of the tongue and palate due to pain and accumulation of saliva.

Medical management of tonsillitis:

- 1) Bed rest
- 2) Plenty of oral fluids
- 3) Analgesics and pain killers

.

Surgical management is Tonsillectomy which is removal of tonsils.

TONSILLECTOMY

Tonsillectomy techniques can be classified into cold and hot procedures. In cold technique, no heat is used, including dissection and snare, which is most commonly done, guillotine, microdebrider, harmonic scalpel, intracapsular tonsillectomy with debrider and cryosurgery. Hot techniques include electrocautery, coblation, radiofrequency and laser tonsillectomy or tonsillotomy(CO₂ or KTP).^{38,39}

“Various methods to perform tonsillectomy.”⁹

1. Cold dissection and snare.
2. Microdebrider-assisted partial tonsillectomy.
3. Bipolar radiofrequency ablation (coblation).
4. Bipolar electrodissection.
5. LASER.
6. Diathermy.
7. Cryosurgery.”

INDICATIONS FOR TONSILLECTOMY(PARADISE CRITERIA).⁸

For a long time, only a trial of value was done by Paradise published in 1984.⁴⁰

Frequency of sore throat events:

- 1)7 or more episodes of tonsillitis in the preceding 1 year.⁴⁰
- 2)5 episodes of tonsillitis in the preceding 2 years.⁴⁰
- 3)3 or more episodes of tonsillitis in the preceding 3 years.⁴⁰

Clinical features (I feature with sore throat).⁴⁰

- 1) Temperature more than 38.3 degree celsius.⁴⁰
- 2) Tender cervical lymph nodes of size more than 2 cm.⁴⁰
- 3) Tonsillar exudate.⁴⁰

4)positive culture for GABHS Treatment:

Antibiotics are administered to proven or suspected cases of GABHS.

Documentation:

Synchronous medical record documentation of each episode and qualifying characters is done. If documentation is insufficient, a clinician will observe two subsequent episodes of throat infection for frequency and clinical features consistent with history.⁴⁰

SIGN GUIDELINES(BOTH CHILDREN AND ADULTS)

SCOTTISH INTERCOLLEGIATE GUIDELINES NETWORK(SIGN) DEVELOPED SIGN 34 IN JANUARY 1999.⁴¹

SIGN 34 outlines the appropriate tonsillectomy indications in adults and children with recurrent tonsillitis.⁴²

For recurrent severe sore throat surgical management by tonsillectomy is recommended in adults and children.⁴¹

These indications remained unchanged in 2010(SIGN 117)⁴¹.The indications will be:

1. Sore throats are due to acute tonsillitis.⁴¹
2. Seven or more episodes of well⁴¹
documented, clinically significant, adequately treated sore throats in one year.⁴¹
3. per year/five or more per two years/three or more per three years⁴¹
4. Symptoms for at least a year.⁴¹
5. Episodes of sore throat are disabling and prevent normal function⁴¹

PITTSBURG CRITERIA⁴³

1)a) At least three episodes of tonsil infection per year for three years.

Five episodes of tonsil infection per year for two years.⁴³

Seven episodes of tonsil infection per year for one year.⁴³

b)Each episode must be characterised by:

Oral temperature 38.3 degrees Celsius.⁴³

Enlarged > 2 cm or tender cervical lymph node⁴³

Positive culture for group-A beta-hemolytic streptococci⁴³

c)Adequate antibiotics must have been administered for suspected or proven streptococcal episodes.⁴³

Each episode is confirmed by examination, and its qualified features are described in the clinical record at the time of occurrence.⁴³

2. Peritonsillar abscess⁴³

3. Chronic tonsillitis persists for at least six months despite appropriate microbial therapy.⁴³

4. Non obstructive symptoms if tonsils are enlarged.Muffled hot potato voice if the child is at least six years old, OSA with or without mouth breathing.⁴³

5. Chronic (minimum six months) enlargement (>2 cm)or tenderness of cervical lymph nodes that persist despite appropriate antibiotic therapy.⁴³

Obstruction

- 1)Tonsillar hyperplasia with obstruction⁴³
- 2)Failure to thrive⁴³
- 3)Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome⁴³
- 4)Speech abnormalities⁴³
- 5)Sleep-related disordered breathing⁴³
- 6)Upper airway obstruction⁴³
- 7)Orofacial and dental abnormalities⁴³
- 8)Lymphoproliferative disorder⁴³
- 9)Cor pulmonale⁴³

Infection:

- 1)Cervical nodes that are abscessed with recurrent or chronic tonsillitis.⁴³
- 2)Tender cervical nodes⁴³
- 3)Halitosis⁴³
- 4)Acute airway obstruction⁴³
- 5)Tonsillolithiasis⁴³
- 6)Persistent tonsillitis wih persistent sore throat⁴³
- 7)Cardiac valve disease⁴³

Neoplasia:⁴³

Suspected Neoplasia, either benign or malignant⁴³

INDICATIONS OF TONSILLECTOMY

The American Academy of Otolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery(AAO-HNS)suggested the following:⁴⁴

Absolute Indications

- 1) Recurrent peritonsillar abscess requiring drainage and unresponsive to medical treatment.⁴⁴
- 2) Recurrent throat infection⁴⁴
- 3) Tonsillitis causing febrile seizures.⁴⁴
- 4)Hypertrophy of the tonsils causing airway obstruction, sleep disorder, and cardiopulmonary complications.⁴⁴
- 5) Suspicion of malignancy requiring biopsy.⁴⁴

Relative Indications.

- 1) Episodic tonsillitis with cervical lymphadenitis suppuration needing drainage.⁴⁴
- 2)Diphtheria carriers⁴⁴
- 3) Streptococcal carriers⁴⁴
- 4) Chronic tonsillitis with bad taste or halitosis⁴⁴
- 5) Patients with valvular heart disease affected by recurrent streptococcal tonsillitis⁴⁴
- 6)Speech abnormalities⁴⁴

As part of another operation

- 1) Uvulopalatopharyngoplasty(UPPP) to treat sleep apnoea⁴⁴
- 2) Glossopharyngeal neurectomy to treat glossopharyngeal neuralgia.⁴⁴
- 3) Branchial fistula⁴⁴
- 4) Parapharyngeal tumor excision⁴⁴
- 5) Eagle's syndrome as a part of removing the elongated styloid process⁴⁴

PREOPERATIVE ASSESSMENT

Elective adenotonsillar surgery requires routine preoperative laboratory study, which remains controversial. If a patient reveals potential bleeding disorders, coagulation parameters must be assessed. In case of bleeding disorders, assays like aPTT and platelet count. Screening for inherited or acquired coagulation disorders uses PT, PFA 100 and bleeding time.

American Academy of Otolaryngology-Head & Neck Surgery recently updated its 2011 guideline on the care and management of paediatric patients who may be candidates for tonsillectomy.⁴⁵

The guideline update group has made solid recommendations for the key action statements(KAS):

1. Clinicians should recommend watchful waiting for recurrent sore throat infection if seven sore throat episodes occur in one year, five years for the last 2 years or 3 years for the last 3 years.⁴⁵
2. In children, clinicians, prior to surgery, administer intraoperatively a single vial of dexamethasone intravenously.⁴⁵
3. Clinicians recommend following tonsillectomy with acetaminophen, ibuprofen or both for pain control.

The guideline update group strongly recommends no administering or prescribing perioperative antibiotics to a child undergoing tonsillectomy.⁴⁵

Clinicians must not administer or prescribe codeine or any medication containing codeine after tonsillectomy in a child less than 12 years.⁴⁵

Clinicians should ask caregivers of children with Obstructive sleep-disordered breathing and tonsillar hypertrophy about comorbid conditions that improve after tonsillectomy, like poor academic performance, growth retardation, asthma, enuresis and behavioral problems.⁴⁵

STEPS OF SURGERY

1) PATIENT POSITION

Rose position given. Under GA, endotracheal intubation was done, and parts were painted and draped. Boyle-Davis mouth gag with ring blade, endotracheal tube in the midline is engaged to retract the tongue and suspended in place using Draffin's bipod and Maguren plate. The split blade of the gag holds the tongue in midline and the endotracheal tube.(Image 9)

The throat is packed with a wet throat pack to prevent aspiration of blood. The gauze is made wet to prevent oxygen entrapment due to minor leaks around the cuff, causing burns if cautery is used for dissection.

IMAGE 8 :TONSIL INSTRUMENTS FOR CONVENTIONAL PROCEDURE

Rose position: The patient is supine and has a pillow under the shoulders for head and neck extension. In young patients, a towel rolled up under the shoulders is critically needed due to the large head size compared to the chest. The head should

not be hanging to avoid ligamentous injury to the cervical spine, which can cause postoperative neck pain. The neck should not be hyperextended.

In Down syndrome patients, shoulder support is avoided due to their lax cervical ligaments, as it can cause subluxation of the cervical spine.(Image 10)

IMAGE 9:ROSE POSITION

2) IDENTIFICATION OF PLANE

Dennis-brown tonsil holding forceps are used to hold the upper pole of the tonsil and pulled medially. The plane is identified between the anterior tonsillar pillar and the tonsil. The incision is made at the mucosal reflection with a scalpel(Waugh's forceps or tonsillar scissors) and carried to the base of the anterior pillars.

Dissection continued till the glistening greyish-white tonsillar capsule is exposed.

3) BLUNT DISSECTION

Gwyne-Evan tonsillar dissector separates the upper pole of the tonsil from the loose areolar tissue attachments to anterior and posterior pillars. This way, the tonsil is separated from its bed using medial traction. The tonsillar capsule is bluntly dissected from peritonsillar tissue using a tonsillar dissector.

Prior to beginning the dissection, the upper pole mobilised, with special attention paid to maintaining the dissector's proximity to the capsule at all times. "Digging" into the fossa results in bleeding and scarring after surgery. The tonsil is grasped by its upper pole, and the surgeon draws it towards the center, then releases the peritonsillar tissues from the capsule until the lower pole is reached..

4) SNARING AND REMOVAL OF TONSIL

The tonsil is snared and separated using Eve's tonsillar snare by passing around the pedicle. Alternatively, the lower pole can also be clamped with curved artery forceps and cut.

The tonsillar fossa is then packed with gauze soaked in hydrogen peroxide and kept for a few minutes to prevent oozing. The bleeders are caught and ligated or cauterized in case of prominent bleeding. The bleeding vessel will be grasped with the tip of Birkett's slender tonsillar hemostatic forceps and Negus curved forceps placed under the tip of straight forceps. The straight forceps will be removed, and silk thread will be placed.

Similarly, tonsils will be removed from the opposite side. When hemostasis is achieved, blood should be cleared from the postnasal space, pharynx and laryngeal inlet. The Boyle Davis mouth gag will be released, and the lower pole will be checked to rule out any bleeding, which was controlled by the gag. The throat packs will be removed, and the swabs will be counted.

ADVANTAGES OF CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY

- 1) Not costly
- 2) Postop bleeding is less compared to coblation tonsillectomy.

DISADVANTAGES OF CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY

- 1) More bleeding and injury to tonsillar pillars, uvula and soft palate
- 2) Capsule preservation is not precise and causes more postoperative pain.

COBLATION TONSILLECTOMY

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE:

The application of plasma technology by Woloszko and Gilbride for tissue ablation was a significant advancement. Meanwhile, Cushing and Bovie popularized radio frequency for various medical purposes like cutting, coagulation, and tissue desiccation. Philip E. Eggers and Hira V. Thapliyal coined the term “coblation,” which means controlled ablation.

K.R. Stalder and J. Woloszko played a crucial role in creating microplasma through electrical charges in a saline environment. This microplasma led to the surgical ablation of tissues, enhancing surgical outcomes. The wand functions like a knife to facilitate tissue ablation and is a disposable electrode.

Coblation tonsillectomy was initially introduced in 2001⁴, following which a significant number of articles were published to confirm its efficacy.

“Coblation involves passing a bipolar radiofrequency current through isotonic saline to convert it into an ionized plasma layer.¹⁶ This layer effectively disrupts intracellular molecular bonds in the tissues, resulting in a vaporization effect. The pooling of saline inside the oral cavity is prevented by surface irrigation and suction.¹⁶”

Coblation generates a substantially low thermal effect compared to electrocautery, estimated between 40 - 70°C⁵, with a subsequent presumption of diminished collateral thermal damage to surrounding tissues. While in electrocautery, which is used in conventional dissection tonsillectomy, it reaches up to 400 - 600°C.^{6,7}

“Coblation tonsillectomy done with assisted procedures like Arthro care, Evac

70 Arthro Wand(Arthro Care, Sunnyvale,CA) handpiece.⁴⁶”

PRINCIPLES OF COBLATION

Coblation is a nonthermal, volumetric technique for tissue removal involving molecular dissection through radiofrequency (RF) energy. This technique utilizes RF energy effectively to remove affected tissue precisely, causing minimal damage to healthy tissue. Running an electric current through a conductive fluid causes the release of a charged layer of particles known as plasma.

The coblation technique is a non-heat-based soft tissue dissolution process, employing bipolar radiofrequency energy. The current from radiofrequency flows through a conductive medium like normal saline, breaking down into sodium and chloride ions. These energized particles have a strong plasma field breaking the organic molecular bonds inside delicate tissues, leading to disintegration. Contrarily, traditional high-frequency electrosurgical devices from the 1950s rely on heat generation for tissue ablation and coagulation, inadvertently causing collateral damage to normal tissues.

STAGES OF PLASMA GENERATION:

The stages of plasma generation utilize Coblation devices at a temperature range of 40-70 degrees Celsius to ensure minimal thermal penetration and gentle tissue removal/dissolution while limiting the impact on surrounding tissues.

The stage of vapour gas piston formation leads to an increase in surface temperature by reducing heat emission. Vapour pulsation leads to tissue ablation.

The amplitude of current across electrodes will be reduced. Electron energy will be dissipated at the metal electrode surface. When coblation is applied intermittently, the recombination of plasma ions, active atoms and molecules causes effective tissue ablation and minimal harm to healthy tissues. It also ensures a constant stage

of vapour film pulsation.

COMPONENTS OF THE COBLATION SYSTEM

The Coblation system comprises essential components like the RF generator(Image 11), foot pedal for control(Image 12), irrigation system(Image 11), and wand(Image 13).

The RF generator, managed by a microprocessor, generates RF signals tailored to the type of wand used. The foot pedal, color-coded for coblation(yellow) and RF cautery(blue) modes, ensures easy use with distinct audio cues for each mode.⁴⁶

Coblation, not requiring a continuous flow of current through tissues, relies on the chemical etching effect of the plasma generated by the wand, which forms a small amount of current through tissues.

Numerous specialized wands are essential for varied otolaryngological surgeries where coblation technology proves beneficial, ranging from adenoid and tonsil wands to nasal and laryngeal wands, each serving specific surgical needs effectively. This generator automatically adjusts the settings as per the type of wand inserted. Coblation and cauterization are the two settings done.⁴⁶

For a tonsil, the recommended settings are: Coblation 7 (Plasma setting) cauterization-3 (Non-plasma setting).The plasma wand used by surgeon has four parts:⁴⁶(Image14.15.16.17,18)

- 1)Irrigation port with an attached saline drip.⁴⁶
- 2)Suction port to remove the debris caused by tissue removal.⁴⁶
- 3)An active electrode array and the return electrode.⁴⁶

- “1. Mode of operation-Dissection, ablation, and coagulation⁴⁶
2. Operating frequency-100Hz⁴⁶
 3. Power consumption -110/240v,50/60 Hz⁴⁶”

**IMAGE 10:RF GENERATOR WITH IRRIGATION
CONTROLLER**

**IMAGE 11: FOOT PEDAL FOR ABLATION AND
COAGULATION**

IMAGE 12 :WAND AND ELECTRODE MECHANISM⁴⁶

IMAGE 13:TONSIL INSTRUMENTS FOR COBLATION

IMAGE 14:PROCEDURE DONE IN STERILISED OT

IMAGE 15: COBLATION TONSILLECTOMY

IMAGE 16: COBLATION WAND

IMAGE 17: TONSILS

The plasma thickness is 100-200 micrometers around active electrodes. The base and active electrodes of coblator is separated by ceramics.

Current will be generated when saline will be flowing through these electrodes.

Saline gets broken down into ions, thereby forming active plasma that ablates tissues.

Coblation is a smokeless procedure. The presence of smoke indicates the presence of tissue in the wand between electrodes. The collector wand should generate a frequency of at least 200 Hz. Frequencies lower than 100 cause neuromuscular excitation if the wand comes in contact with tissues.

Bipolar cauterization of large vessels can be done with the same wand.

Modes of Coblation.⁴⁷

1) Ablation mode: The performance of wand on increasing the RF setting from 1-9, changes from thermal to ablative when there is creation and increase in plasma intensity.⁴⁷

When the controller setting in coblation mode increases, the plasma field increases in size and decreases the thermal effect accordingly.⁴⁷

2) Coagulation mode: All coblation wands are designed to operate in coagulation mode for hemostasis during surgery. Since the wand is bipolar, it sends energy through the desired tissue area through a resistive heating process.^{46,47}

3) The efficiency of ablation can be improved by^{46,47}

1. Intermittent application of ablation mode^{46,47}

2. Copious irrigation of normal saline^{46,47}

3. Plasma generated using cold saline plasma is more efficient in ablating tissues.^{46,47}

“Otolaryngological surgeries where coblation technology is useful are.^{47,48,49}

1) Adenotonsillectomy^{47,48,49}

2) Tongue base reduction^{47,48,49}

3) Tongue channeling^{47,48,49}

4) Uvulo palato pharyngoplasty^{47,48,49}

5) Cordectomy

6) Removal of benign lesions of larynx including papilloma^{47,48,49}

7) Kashima’s procedure for bilateral abductor paralysis

8) Turbinate reduction

9) Nasal polypectomy^{47,48,49}”

“There are different types of wands available to perform coblation procedures optimally.

Tonsil and adenoid wands are commonly used for all oropharyngeal surgeries.

This wand will have to be slightly bent to reach the adenoid.^{47,48}

The laryngeal wand is of two types—

Normal laryngeal wand. That is used to ablate laryngeal mass lesions.

A mini laryngeal wand is used to remove small polyps from vocal folds.^{47,48}

The main advantage of a mini laryngeal wand is its ability to reach up to the subglottic area.⁴⁷

A nasal wand and nasal tunneling wand are commonly used for turbinate reduction. A separate tunneling wand is for tongue base reduction.”

ADVANTAGES OF COBLATION TONSILLECTOMY:

1. Less bleeding and causes precise ablation of tissues.
2. The capsule can be preserved under magnification and causes less postoperative pain.
3. Tonsillar reduction surgeries performed in young children.
4. Less damage to adjacent tissues.

DISADVANTAGES OF COBLATION:

1. The cost of the wand is high
2. Reusing the wand following coblation increases the chance of secondary infections/secondary bleeding.
3. Reuse of the wand will not lead to optimal plasma generation.
4. Post-op secondary bleeding is more common in coblation tonsillectomy than in conventional tonsillectomy.

POSTOPERATIVE ADVISE

- 1) Nil per orally for the next 4 hours until fully recovered from anesthesia.
- 2) The head end should be low, and the patient should be placed in the left lateral position to permit free respiration and allow any blood and secretions to flow out of the mouth and nose. This prevents upper airway obstruction.
- 3)The patient will be monitored for vital signs. Indicators of bleeding like tachycardia, hypotension, and frequent swallowing should be checked for.
- 4) Inj Dexamethasone intraoperatively and 6 hours after surgery acts as anti-inflammatory, antipyretic and anti-emetic.
- 5) Inj Dynapar or Paracetamol can be given. In children, acetaminophen can be put

as a suppository. The incidence of vomiting, the local temperature rise, earache, odynophagia, and change in voice should not cause any worry. Tonsillar slough occurs postoperatively.

POSTOPERATIVE DIET:

- 1) A liquid, soft diet with cold items like ice cream, preferably vanilla, pudding, iced juice, and yogurt.
- 2) For 1 week- Milk, honey, minced vegetable soup, smashed rice and fruits.
- 3) Next 1 week- Normal diet. Hot and spicy food items should be avoided for 1 week. Physical exertion should be avoided for 14 days.

COMPLICATIONS OF TONSILLECTOMY

INTRAOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS

1) Primary Haemorrhage

Occurs at the time of operation. It can happen if a patient with acute tonsils/quinsy /large para tonsillar vein is present. Bleeding is managed by pressure, packing, ligation or electrocautery, slipknot ties, and hemostatic topical agents like Avitene. If these measures fail, external carotid artery ligation is the last choice.

2) Operative trauma

Faulty placement of the tongue blade causes injury to the tongue, lips, tonsillar pillars and posterior pharyngeal wall. Burn injury on using cautery.

3) Aspiration of blood

Using an uncuffed endotracheal tube, the aspiration of blood and secretion occurs into the lower airway. It can be prevented by placing the patient in the Rose position

and placing a throat pack on either side of the endotracheal tube before surgery. After surgery, proper irrigation with saline is done to remove clots and tissues.

4) Airway compromise

It occurs due to malposition/kinking or compression of the endotracheal tube. It can cause laryngeal trauma and spasm. Pulmonary oedema can occur in cases of prolonged airway obstruction.

5) Airway fire

Airway fire can occur when using diathermy in the presence of anesthetic gas leakage. It can be prevented by placing wet gauze around the endotracheal tube.

POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS

1) Primary and Reactionary haemorrhage

Primary haemorrhage -occurs during the surgical procedure. Reactionary haemorrhage occurs within 24 hours.

Bleeding can occur due to lodgement of the clot, increased venous pressure due to cough, slippage of ligature or vasodilation of blood vessels.

The clipping action of superior constrictor muscle on the vessels that pass through it will be prevented due to the presence of a clot. There will be vomiting of blood with active bleeding from the tonsillar fossa. There will be signs of hypotension, hypoxia and hypovolemia, airway, breathing and circulation should be assessed.

If the patient is fully conscious, then the patient is made to sit to spit out blood and to keep the airway clear. If the patient is unconscious, regular suctioning of the oral cavity will be done. The patient is then rehydrated. If the patient is intubated, the oropharynx is suctioned, and the clot is removed from the tonsillar fossa, followed by ligation or cauterizing of the bleeding vessel.

If not controlled, gel foam is placed in the tonsillar fossa, and the anterior pillar is sutured with the posterior pillars. If the bleeding cannot be stopped, then ligation of the external carotid artery in the neck is done. Ryles tube gastric lavage will be done, and the hemoglobin level will be checked postoperatively.

2) Surgical trauma

Trauma to the uvula during excessive resection of anterior pillars or manipulation during surgery can cause severe edema during excessive resection of anterior pillars or manipulation during surgery. It can be managed with Inj Dexamethasone and gargles.

3) Pulmonary complications

Lung collapse, abscess or pneumonia can occur due to inhalation of blood or tonsillar tissue. In children undergoing adenotonsillectomy, respiratory compromise can occur due to pulmonary edema caused by prolonged airway obstruction (OSA). The arterial blood gas analysis for carbon dioxide and pulse oximetry for oxygen saturation should be analysed. The patient should be managed in the intensive care unit with CPAP, diuretics and ventilatory support.

4) Dehydration and pain

It occurs if the patient refuses to eat and drink orally. Ensure proper hydration intraop and postop. Inj. Dexamethasone postop helps the patient return to a normal diet and activity faster. Excessive pain with referred otalgia can occur.

5) Infection

Infection of the tonsillar fossa occurs if the child is operated on during acute infection or if instruments are not properly sterilised. If a child develops halitosis, a penicillin group of antibiotics along with metronidazole should be given for seven days.

INTERMEDIATE COMPLICATIONS:

1) Secondary haemorrhage

Bleeding occurs more than 24 hours after surgery between the fifth and tenth postoperative day. It occurs due to premature separation of the membranes due to sepsis, which releases toxins. There may be blood-stained sputum. Clot removal, systemic antibiotics, hydrogen peroxide gargles, and topical adrenaline application can be managed if severe blood loss transfusion can be considered. If bleeding is severe, the anterior and posterior pillars should be approximated with mattress sutures. As the tissues are friable, ligation should be avoided.

LATE COMPLICATIONS:

1) Scarring of pillars and soft palate

2) Velopharyngeal insufficiency

3) Incomplete removal of tonsils leads to tonsillar remnants that can cause repeated infection, requiring complete removal under anesthesia.

4) Temporary taste distortion due to pressure on the tongue or can be permanent if surgical traction occurs on a lingual branch of the glossopharyngeal nerve.

5) Voice change

6) Paralysis of glossopharyngeal nerve.

7) Pharyngeal stenosis or oropharyngeal stenosis that occurs as an inflammatory process. It can be treated using injection of Triamcinolone, lysis of adhesions and rotational and advancement mucosal flap placement.

8) Hypertrophy of lingual tonsils as compensation for removal of palatine tonsils.

CONTRAINDICATIONS FOR TONSILLECTOMY

- 1) Presence of acute infection of tonsils, acute infection of the upper respiratory tract.
- 2) Haemoglobin level less than 10 g%
- 3) Children under 3 years of age or pregnant ladies.
- 4) Children with palatal defects.
- 5) Patients with bleeding or coagulation disorders like aplastic anaemia, haemophilia, leukaemia or purpura.
- 6) Patients with uncontrolled systemic illnesses like diabetes, hypertension, asthma, or cardiac diseases.
- 7) Tonsillectomy avoided during the time of menstruation. Menstruation is no longer a contraindication for surgery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN : PROSPECTIVE STUDY

SOURCE OF DATA

All patients undergoing tonsillectomy in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology, BLDE (Deemed to be University) Shri B. M . Medical College and research center, Vijayapura. The Study will be on patients aged 5–55 years undergoing tonsillectomy.

The period of study is from September 2022 to March 2024.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

1. Patients undergoing tonsillectomy in Department of Otorhinolaryngology, BLDE (Deemed to be University) Shri B. M . Medical College and research center, Vijayapura BLDE.
2. Each case will be screened from the outpatient department and will undergo general physical examination, local ENT examination, and laboratory and radiological examination. Fitness for surgery will be taken.
3. The data will be collected in the form of clinical examination ,mode of surgery,time taken for surgery,intraoperative & postoperative blood loss,postoperative pain,time required to return to normal diet and activity.
4. Postoperative pain and time required to return to normal diet and activity outcomes will be obtained via a questionnaire given to the patient or caregiver.

5. Patients will be followed up postoperatively for five days with antibiotics and for 10 days to observe hemorrhage/pain. Postoperative bleeding from the tonsillar fossa will be assessed by the type of procedure that the patient will undergo and the day on which it occurred, and the measures that will be taken to stop it. Post operative patients are followed up immediate post op day 1, 5th day and 10th day.

SAMPLE SIZE:

Using G*Power ver. 3.1.9.4 software for sample size calculation, The Operation time based on method Coblation (Mean=13.4, SD=7.0) and Conventional (Mean=20.4, SD=9.7), this study requires a total sample size of 110 (for each group 55, assuming equal group sizes). So to achieve a power of 99% for detecting a difference means (t-tests-Means: Difference between two independent means (two groups)).¹⁶

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The data obtained is entered in a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analyses are performed using a statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) (Version 20). Results are presented as Mean, SD, counts and percentages, and diagrams. For normally distributed continuous variables between the two groups will be compared using an independent sample t-test. For not normally distributed variables, the Mann-Whitney U test is used. Categorical variables between the two groups are compared using the Chi-square test/Fisher's exact test. <0.05 will be considered statistically significant. All statistics are performed two-tailed.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- 1) Patients aged between 5 and 55 years.
- 2) Recurrent attacks of acute tonsillitis—7 or more episodes in the preceding year
OR 5 or more episodes in each of the preceding 2 years or 3 or more episodes in each of the preceding 3 years.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- 1) Bleeding and clotting disorders.
- 2) Adenoid hypertrophy
- 3) Active peritonsillar abscess.
- 4) Respiratory tract infection
- 5) Pregnancy and lactation
- 6) Uncontrolled chronic systemic illness.
- 7) Patients with serous otitis media

METHODS

1) All patients will be explained in detail about the procedure and involvement in this study, and voluntary consent for surgery will be taken from each patient.

2) A total sample of 110 patients will be taken and randomly put into groups A and B.

3) In Group A, tonsillectomy will be performed by coblation method, and in Group B by conventional method. Patients will be randomized to either dissection or coblation.

4) After obtaining the history of chief complaints like sore throat, odynophagia, past history, personal history a thorough general, systemic and local ENT examination will be done and then the patient will be subjected to basic investigations for fitness for surgery under general anesthesia. Coagulation profile will be done in doubtful cases. Pre op anaesthetic workup will be done. Patients with serous otitis media are ruled out after Impedence audiometry and adenoid hypertrophy patients ruled out using diagnostic nasal endoscopy.

5) The same surgeon will be perform tonsillectomy procedure either by the Dissection & snare method or Coblation method using Evac 70 coblation wand using 6 or 7 setting.

6) Preoperatively, a single dose of Amoxicillin-Clavulanic acid

injection will be given to all the patients.

7) Patient will be kept for NBM for 6-8 hours prior to surgery. Necessary part preparation for surgery done.

8) The time taken for surgery will be measured from the time of insertion of Boyle-Davis mouth gag to final haemostasis and removal of mouth gag. Time taken will be recorded in minutes.

9) Intraoperative blood loss will be measured by Calorimetric method (swab weighing technique).⁵⁰

To reduce the quantity of saliva and secretion the oral cavity wiped with separate gauze piece along with premedication of atropine half an hour before surgery.

All the blood lost will be collected in suction bottle. The fresh gauze piece is taken to have a constant weight of 2 gm. Once the tonsils are removed its thoroughly squeezed into a gauze piece. The swabs and gauze piece used for procedure will be weighed using weighing scale.

In the coblation method, blood loss will be calculated after deducting the amount of saline used from the total collection in suction jar.

The formula:⁵⁰(TABLE 3)

Weight of cotton swab/gauze before use= $y = 2 \text{ gm}(\text{fixed})$ [no of swab/gauze used $\times 2 \text{ gm}$]
Weight of cotton swab soaked/gauze soaked with blood = $x \text{ g}^{50}$
Weight of blood lost = $(x-y) \text{ gm}^{50}$
Specific gravity of blood= 1.0555^{50}
Quantity of blood lost= $x-y/1.055 \text{g} = A$
Total fluid in suction jar [Blood(z) + known amount of saline used for procedure in case of coblation(150ml)]
Quantity of blood in suction jar = $z - 150 \text{ ml} = B$
In case of conventional saline is taken as nil
Total intraop blood loss during surgery = $x-y/1.055 \text{g} + z - 150 \text{ ml} = A+B^{50}$

TABLE 3: CALORIMETRIC SWAB WEIGHING FORMULA⁵⁰

Hydrogen peroxide soaked gauze pieces are excluded.

10) Patient will be extubated after achieving haemostasis, patient will be shifted to recovery room and monitored for airway obstruction and signs of

bleeding. Intraop and post op Inj. Dexamethasone is given to reduce inflammation. Patient will be kept in left lateral position with oxygen mask if needed.

11) Patient advised to break NBM after 4 hours and to take fluids and soft diet. Inj paracetamol/Inj dynapar given according to age and weight. Betadine and hydrogen peroxide gargling will be started by evening. Patient will be shifted to ward if postop recovery is uneventful.

12) Patient will be monitored for post operative haemorrhage by observing for trickling of blood or active bleeding in ppw. Presence of any clots should also be noted. Patient monitored for 24 hours for reactionary bleeding and if present managed properly.

13) Postoperative outcomes for pain and time required to return to normal activity will be obtained via a questionnaire administered to the patient or caregiver. The questionnaire was in both English and the local language.

14) Patients will be followed up postoperatively for five days with antibiotics and for 10 days to observe hemorrhage/pain. Patient will be discharged on POD-2. Discharge will be delayed if any complication occurs. Patient will be in contact after discharge.

15) Post op pain will be assessed by stopping intravenous pain killers from POD-1 and changing to tablets. Patient will only take medication in case of severe pain. Patient was advised to take more ice cream.

Post op pain assessed using Wong-Baker Faces Pain Rating Scale.⁵¹(Image 19)

IMAGE 18: WONG-BAKER FACES PAIN RATING SCALE⁵¹

“The pain scale was developed by Donna Wong and Connie Baker. This scale shows series of faces ranging from a happy face at 0, or “no hurt” to a crying face at 10 or “hurts worst”. Based on the faces and written descriptions, the patient chooses the face that describes the level of pain.⁵²”

"0-No hurt, 2-hurts little bit, 4-hurts little more, 6-hurts even more, 8-hurts whole lot, 10-hurts worst.⁵³Patients will be followed up for POD-1,POD-5 and POD-10.

16)Patients time required to return to normal diet and activity is measured using Chang and Myatt Questionnaires.⁵⁴(Table 4)

Patient followed up from POD-1 to POD-10. The activities which return to normal will be marked and the POD when the patient attains all the activities will be taken as final.

1)Did child miss school/day care? ⁵³	A)Yes	B)No	C)Does not attend school/daycare	
2)Have you/your child been drinking? ⁵³	A)Not at all	B)Have sips when forced	C)Sips on their own	D)Drinking as usual
3)Have you/your child been eating? ⁵³	A)Not at all	B)A few mouthful	C)Eating less than normal	D)Eating normally
4)What kind of foods have you/your child been	A)Has not been eating	B)Juices and fluids	C)Soft foods	D)Regular diet
5)Have you/your child been talking?	A)Not at all	B)A few words	C)In a normal voice but less talkative than usual	D)Talking as usual
6)Have you/your child been active?	A)Not lying in bed	B)Reluctant up in bed	C)Sitting up in bed	D)Getting out of bed
7)Has your child been playing?	A)Not at all	B)Playing in bed	C)Getting up to watch others	D)Getting up to play
8)How have your/your child's mood been?	A)Silent	B)Unhappy and miserable	C)A little upset	D)Cheerful,Content
9)Did you have to miss work today?	A)Yes	B)No	C)Would not have worked anyway	
10)Did you complete your planned activities/errands today? ⁵³	A)Yes	B)Some of them	C)No	

TABLE 4:CHANG AND MYATT QUESTIONNAIRES⁵⁴

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All characteristics were summarized descriptively. For continuous variables, the summary statistics of mean \pm standard deviation (SD) were used. For categorical data, the number and percentage were used in the data summaries and diagrammatic presentation. Chi-square (χ^2) test was used for association between two categorical variables.

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

The formula for the chi-square statistic used in the chi square test is:

The subscript “c” is the degree of freedom. “O” is observed value and E is expected value.

$$C = (\text{number of rows} - 1) \times (\text{number of columns} - 1)$$

The difference of the means of analysis variables between two independent

$$t = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

groups was tested by unpaired t test.

The t statistic to test whether the means are different can be calculated as follows:

If the p-value was < 0.05 , then the results were considered to be statistically significant otherwise it was considered as not statistically significant. Data were analysed using SPSS software v.23 (IBM Statistics, Chicago, USA) and Microsoft office 2007.

where \bar{x}_1 = mean of sample 1

\bar{x}_2 = mean of sample 2

n_1 = number of subjects in sample 1

n_2 = number of subjects in sample 2

$$s_1^2 = \text{variance of sample 1} = \frac{\sum(x_1 - \bar{x}_1)^2}{n_1}$$

$$s_2^2 = \text{variance of sample 2} = \frac{\sum(x_2 - \bar{x}_2)^2}{n_2}$$

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

A hospital-based prospective study is conducted on 110 patients to compare coblation and conventional tonsillectomy based on the time taken for surgery, intraoperative & postoperative blood loss, postoperative pain, time required to return to normal diet and activity and incidence of reactionary & secondary hemorrhage.

1)SEX DISTRIBUTION:

Out of the 110 patients, the total number of female patients in both coblation and conventional tonsillectomy was 66(60%), and male patients were 44(40.0%). Coblation and conventional had equal numbers of female 33(60%) and male 22(40%)patients. Females are more in our study, with an equal number of both sexes in each group.

Gender (Male or Female)	COBLATION	CONVENTIONAL	Total	Chi square test	Significant value
Female	33	33	66	0.000	P=1.000
	60.0%	60.0%	60.0%		
Male	22	22	44		
	40.0%	40.0%	40.0%		
Total	55	54	109		
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
Statistically Insignificant					

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO GENDER.

FIGURE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO GENDER

2) AGE GROUP DISTRIBUTION

Out of the 110 patients, 55 patients underwent coblation and 55 patients underwent conventional tonsillectomy. In 110 patients 32 patients were less than 10 years of age. 50 patients were in the age group of 10-19, 18 patients were in the age group 20-29, 5 patients were in the age group 30-39, 4 patients were above 40. The study showed that the least number of patients were in the age group above 40 years.

The maximum number of patients being in age group 10-19 years of age.

Age(Years)	COBLATION	CONVENTIONAL	Total	Chi square test	Significant value
< 10	16	16	32	0.271	P=0.992
	29.1%	29.6%	29.4%		
10 - 19	26	24	50		
	47.3%	44.4%	45.9%		
20 - 29	9	9	18		
	16.4%	16.7%	16.5%		
30 - 39	2	3	5		
	3.6%	5.6%	4.6%		
40+	2	2	4		
	3.6%	3.7%	3.7%		
Total	55	54	109		
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
Statistically Insignificant					

TABLE 6 :DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO AGE

FIGURE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO AGE

3.DURATION OF OPERATIVE TIME IN MINUTES

Intraoperative time taken for coblation and conventional tonsillectomy is compared. The time taken for the procedure was calculated in minutes for both coblation and conventional tonsillectomy.

The time taken for surgery will be measured from the time of insertion of Boyle-Davis mouth gag to final haemostasis and removal of mouthgag.

The mean operative duration in coblation group (29.64 ± 7.352)min was less than conventional group (53.51 ± 13.434)min with a p value of 0.0001 which is significant.

OPERATIVE TIME IN MINS	COBLATION		CONVENTIONAL		Mann Whitney Test	Significant value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
	29.64	7.352	53.51	13.434	132.500	P=0.0001
Statistically significant(p<0.05)						

TABLE 7 :DISTRIBUTION OF PROCEDURE ACCORDING TO OPERATIVE TIME

FIGURE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF PROCEDURE ACCORDING TO OPERATIVE TIME

4.INTRAOPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS

Coblation tonsillectomy was done for 55 patients and conventional tonsillectomy was done for 55 patients in the study. The intra operative blood loss for conventional tonsillectomy was in the range of (51.45±12.521)ML and for coblation tonsillectomy was in the range of (88.9±16.992)ML. Blood loss in ML was compared to be more for conventional because of time take for coagulation to happen. T value was 69.000 and P value 0.0001 which is statistically significant.

INTRA- OPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS IN ML	COBLATION		CONVENTIONAL		Mann Whitney Test	Significant value
	Mean	Std Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	69.000	P=0.0001
	51.45	12.521	88.89	16.992		
Statistically significant(P value <0.05)						

**ABLE 8:DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO
INTRAOPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS**

The intraoperative blood loss was managed in case of coblation by coagulation using wand and in case of conventional method by bipolar cautery or ligature of bleeding points. In all patients bleeding if present was controlled meticulously. In patients mostly superior and inferior pole bleed was seen. Pillar injury in patients was minimal.

FIGURE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO INTRAOPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS

POST OPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS

The complications are reactionary and secondary haemorrhage

5. INCIDENCE OF REACTIONARY HAEMORRHAGE

Reactionary haemorrhage occurs within first 24 hours of surgery .This is controlled by application of pressure/removal of clot.If not controlled ligation or cauterisation is needed in OT.In both coblation group and coventional group there was no incidence of haemorrhage and reactionary post op blood loss is constant.There was minimal oozing of blood which was controlled by cold water gargles which was negligible.

Post op bloodloss reactionary (in ML)	COBLATION	CONVENTIONAL	Total	Chi square test	Significant value
Absent	55	55	110	0.000	P=constant
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
Present	0	0	0		
	0.0%	0.0%	0		
Total	55	55	110		
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
No statistics are computed because post op blood loss-reactionary is a constant.					

TABLE 9 :DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO INCIDENCE OF REACTIONARY HAEMORRHAGE

FIGURE 5 :DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO INCIDENCE OF REACTIONARY HAEMORRHAGE

6.INCIDENTE OF SECONDARY HAEMORRHAGE

Secondary haemorrhage occurs 24 hours after the surgical procedure due to sepsis or premature separation of membrane. In both coblation group and conventional group there was no incidence of haemorrhage and secondary post op blood loss is constant.

Post op secondary blood loss (in ML)	COBLATION	CONVENTIONAL	Total	Chi square test	Significant value
Absent	55	55	110	0.000	P=Constant
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
Present	0	0	0		
	0.0%	0.0%	0		
Total	55	55	110		
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
No statistics are computed because post op blood loss-secondary is a constant.					

TABLE 10 :DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO INCIDENCE OF SECONDARY HAEMORRHAGE

FIGURE 6 :DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO INCIDENCE OF SECONDARY HAEMORRHAGE

7.POST OPERATIVE PAIN

The post operative pain was followed up using Wong Baker Faces pain scale on POD-1,POD-5 and POD-10.In first POD, coblation tonsillectomy pain score was (6.80±1.253) and conventional was (8.25±1.158).In the fifth POD, pain score for coblation tonsillectomy was (5.20±1.193) and conventional tonsillectomy was (5.89 ±1.462).In the tenth POD, pain score for coblation tonsillectomy was (1.02±1.269) and conventional tonsillectomy was (3.31±1.597). The post op pain score on POD 1,POD-5 and POD-10 was significant.Pain occurs due to delayed healing and exposure of glossopharyngeal nerve.

POST OP DAY	COBLATION		CONVENTIONAL		Mann Whitney Test	Significant value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
POST OP DAY1	6.80	1.253	8.25	1.158	641.000	P=0.0001
POST OP DAY5	5.20	1.193	5.89	1.462	1128.500	P=0.012
POST OP DAY10	1.02	1.269	3.31	1.597	455.000	P=0.0001
Statistically significant(p value<0.05)						

TABLE 11:DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO INCIDENCE OF POSTOPERATIVE PAIN

FIGURE 7 :DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO INCIDENCE OF POSTOPERATIVE PAIN

8.TIME REQUIRED TO RETURN TO NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY

The time required to return to normal diet and activity is calculated using Chang and Myatt Questionnaires⁵⁴.The mean days within which patients who underwent coblation tonsillectomy is 4.29±1.165 days and conventional tonsillectomy is 8.05±1.682 days.The coblation group was found to recover earlier than conventional group.P value was 0.0001 which is statistically significant.Mean return to normal general condition was 4 days in coblation and 8 days in conventional.

TIME REQUIRED FOR NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY	COBLATION		CONVENTIONAL		Mann Whitney Test	Significant value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
	4.29	1.165	8.05	1.682	131.500	P=0.0001
Statistically significant						

TABLE 12:DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO TIME REQUIRED TO RETURN TO NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY.

FIGURE 8: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO TIME REQUIRED TO RETURN TO NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY.

DISCUSSION

Tonsillectomy is one of the most routine surgical procedures in recent years.⁵⁵

Traditional dissection tonsillectomy has remained the gold standard for tonsil removal.⁵⁶

Traditional tonsillectomy leaves the wound open to heal by secondary intention. It can lead to pain and bleeding as the two major postoperative complications.⁵⁷

Wound recovery lasting more extended periods of up to fifteen days is not uncommon.

It can lead to the risk of tonsillar bleeding.^{58,59}

Coblation tonsillectomy was introduced in 2001.⁴

Articles had been published to either confirm its efficacy^{58,61} or to reject its unsatisfactory or unproven outcomes with cost-effectiveness.^{62,63}

The NICE guidelines have suggested that coblation is associated with decreased postoperative pain when compared with bipolar diathermy; however, outcomes may be different for that of monopolar diathermy or cold dissection.⁶⁰

Our study compared coblation tonsillectomy with conventional tonsillectomy in 110 patients.

AGE DISTRIBUTION

Of the 110 patients, 55 underwent coblation, and 55 underwent conventional tonsillectomy. This study showed that the maximum number of patients were in the age group of 10-19 years, and the least were in the age group above 40 years. The 10-19 age group had 50 patients, and 40 plus had 4 patients.

Mostafa El Taher *et al.*, in their study of 1004 patients in 2017, showed that the mean age was 10.4 years.¹⁵

Jyolsna Nelson *et al.*, in their study population of 52 patients in 2023, showed that most of the study population (59.6%) was in the age group of 4–8 years. Only 11.5% of the study population was above 20 years old.⁶⁴

K.Muthubabu *et al.*, in their study on 60 patients in the age group 5-40 years, a maximum number of patients(40%) were in the age group of 6-10 years.¹⁴

Vyas S *et al.*, in their study on 62 patients, the maximum number of patients were in the age group 10-19 years.¹⁷

The mean age group of patients is variable in our study and all these studies as patients were randomly selected with a fixed age range in mind.

GENDER DISTRIBUTION

Out of the 110 patients in our study, the total number of female patients in both coblation and conventional tonsillectomy was 66(60%), and male patients were 44(40.0%). Coblation and conventional had equal numbers of females 33(60%) and males 22(40%) patients. Females are more in our study, with an equal number of both sexes in each group.

Mostafa El Taher *et al.*, in their study of 1004 patients in 2017, showed that the coblation group had 507 patients, with 277 females(54.6%) and 230 males(45.4%). In a conventional group of 497 patients, there was 274 females(55.1%) and 223 males(44.9%). Females are more in this study.¹⁵

Sung-Moon Hong *et al.*, in their study of 80 patients in 2013, found that 31 were males and 49 were females. There were more females in this study.⁶⁵

Mohammed S *et al.*, in their study of 50 patients in 2022, the total number of males in the study was 27 (54%), and females were 23(46%). Males were more in the study.⁶⁶

Jyolsna Nelson *et al.*, in their study population of 52 patients in 2023, showed that 25(48.1%) patients were male, and 27 (51.9%) were female. Males were more in this study.⁶⁴

The study showed that there was no significance of gender in our research, and the studies compared.

INTRAOPERATIVE TIME

In our study, conventional tonsillectomy took more time, 53.51 ± 13.434 min, compared to coblation tonsillectomy, 29.64 ± 7.352 min, which was significant with a P value < 0.0001 .

Dipesh G Darji *et al.*, 2020, in their study on 54 patients, showed that the mean operation time was 25 - 30 minutes in coblation tonsillectomy and 40 - 45 minutes for conventional tonsillectomy. Coblation took less time than traditional.² It was statistically significant with P value < 0.005 .²

Mostafa El Taher *et al.*, in their study of 1004 patients in 2017, showed that the mean operative time was less for coblation (10.63 ± 2.45) min than conventional tonsillectomy (30.66 ± 8.66) min. It was statistically significant (P value < 0.000).¹⁶

Mohammed Saeed *et al.*, in their study of 50 patients in 2022, the mean operative time was less for coblation, 20.2 min compared to a mean of 31.2 min using conventional cold dissection tonsillectomy. The difference between the two procedures was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).⁶⁶

Sohan Lal Jat *et al.*, in 2022, in 70 patients study, the mean operative time among the coblation group was less, 18.24 ± 5.37 min than traditional group, 30.04 ± 7.08 min. It was found that coblation tonsillectomy takes relatively less time than conventional tonsillectomy, and this difference was found to be statistically significant P value < 0.001 .⁶⁷

Omrani M *et al.*, 2012 in their study of 94 patients, showed that the mean operative time of coblation tonsillectomy was less, (27.3 ± 4.8) minutes than for conventional tonsillectomy (31 ± 5.4) minutes. This study showed that the mean operative time was significantly less for coblation tonsillectomy (P value < 0.001).⁶⁸

INTRAOPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS

The mean intraoperative blood loss was 51.45 ± 12.521 ML for coblation and 88.89 ± 16.992 ML for conventional. The blood loss was comparatively higher for the conventional than the coblation method and was controlled appropriately. It was statistically significant with a P value < 0.0001 .

K Muthubabu *et al.*, in 2018, in 60 patients, the mean intraoperative blood loss in the dissection and snare method was 49 ml which was more than coblation method (21 ml). The difference was statistically significant with p-value (0.001).¹⁴

Omrani M *et al.*, in their study of 1004 patients, showed that intraoperative blood loss was 103.4 ± 28.7 ml for coblation compared to traditional method 161.5 ± 46.4 which was more. It was significant with p-value (0.001)⁶⁸

M.Nallasivam MS *et al.*, in 2017 in 50 patients, showed that the blood loss in the coblation method was less, 19 ml compared to the conventional method which was 43 ml. The difference was statistically significant with a p-value (0.001).⁶⁹

Sohan Lal Jat *et al.*, 2022 in 70 patients in 2022 showed that blood loss in coblation was 82.79 ± 21.13 ML and traditional tonsillectomy was 150.4 ± 37.91 ML. It showed that blood loss was significantly less in coblation tonsillectomy with a p-value (0.001).⁶⁷

Stefan Konsulov *et al.*, in their study of 60 patients in 2017, the average blood loss in the conventional method was 97.5 ± 12.13 ML which was more than the coblation method 27.1 ± 14.28 which was .It was statistically significant with a p-value (0.001).⁷⁰

Rakesh S *et al.*, in 2012, in 60 adult patients, showed that the coblation side blood loss was less, 11 ML compared to conventional side blood loss of 34 ML. The difference was statistically significant with a p-value (0.001).⁷²

POSTOPERATIVE HEMORRHAGE

The incidence of postoperative complications like hemorrhage was insignificant in both coblation and conventional tonsillectomy.

There is no incidence of reactionary hemorrhage in either coblation or conventional tonsillectomy. No statistics are computed because reactionary post-op hemorrhage is a constant. A few cases reported minimal oozing of blood, which was controlled by asking patients to do cold water gargles. There was no incidence of secondary hemorrhage in either coblation or conventional tonsillectomy. No statistics are computed because secondary post-op hemorrhage is a constant.

In 2018, in 60 patients, K. Muthubabu *et al.*, showed no incidence of reactionary or secondary hemorrhage in both coblation and conventional study .¹⁴

Divi *et al.*, in 1672 patients from 1993 to 2003, found no difference between postoperative hemorrhage rates for coblation versus non coblation methods. The postoperative bleed rate for non-coblation tonsillectomy was 6.1%.The bleeding rate for coblation tonsillotomy was 5.9%.⁷¹ There was no statistical difference ($P = 0.93$) between bleed rates for coblation versus non coblation techniques.⁷¹

Rakesh S *et al.*, in his study done in 2012, in 60 adult patients who had undergone comparative study of coblation and conventional tonsillectomy, showed that there was no case of reactionary or secondary hemorrhage in both groups.⁷²

Stefan Konsulov *et al.*, in their study of 60 patients in 2017, showed no incidence of secondary hemorrhage in either coblation or conventional tonsillectomy.⁷⁰

POSTOPERATIVE PAIN

The postoperative pain score was found to be more for conventional than coblation tonsillectomy. Post operative pain score on POD 1 for coblation was (6.80 ± 1.2) and conventional was (8.25 ± 1.158); POD 5 pain score for coblation (5.20 ± 1.193) and conventional (5.89 ± 1.462) and for POD 10 pain score for coblation (1.02 ± 1.269) and conventional was (3.31 ± 1.597). It was statistically significant with a P value < 0.0001 for both POD 1 and POD-10. POD -5 had p- value < 0.012 .

Nallasivam MS *et al.*, in 2017, in 50 patients, showed that 60-70 % of patients who had undergone coblation had less pain than conventional. The mean post-op pain score on 1st, 2nd and 7th postoperative days for coblation was 3.92, 3.64 and 2.74, respectively and for conventional, it was 7.42, 6.20, and 3.52, respectively. The P value was ($P \text{ value} = 0.01$), which was significant.⁶⁹

Sohan Lal Jat *et al.*, in 2022, a 70-patient study showed that the mean post-op pain score in the coblation procedure was 3.2 ± 1.47 , less than traditional tonsillectomy 6.11 ± 1.61 , which was found to be significant with ($P \text{ value} < 0.001$).⁶⁷

Dr.Saadhya Shukla *et al.*, in 2022, in 50 patients, compared post-op pain scores using the VAS.The pain score for POD 1,3 and 7 was 7.46, 6.28, and 3.52, respectively for coblation which was less than the scores for conventional,4.02, 3.06, and 2.14. The result was significant, with a p value less than 0.001.⁷³

TIME TAKEN TO RETURN TO NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY

The time required to return to regular diet and activity was less for coblation(4.29±1.165) than conventional(8.05±1.682) tonsillectomy. It was statistically significant with a P value <0.05.

Dipesh G Darji *et al.*, in 2020, in their study on 54 patients, post-op return to normal activities was less for coblation (5-7 days) than conventional tonsillectomy which took 10-12 days.It was statistically significant with p value<0.001²

Mostafa El Taher *et al.*, in their study of 1004 patients in 2017, showed that the mean time required to return to a normal diet was shorter for the coblation group than conventional group(5.00± 1.41 vs. 9.95 ± 1.98 days)(p-value <0.05) respectively. The return to normal general activity was earlier in coblation than conventional (10.30± 2.80 vs. 13.59± 3.74 days)(p value <0/05). The study showed significant results with P value<0.001.¹⁶

Omrani M *et al.*, 2012 in their study of 94 patients, showed that return to normal general condition was earlier in coblation than conventional(7.6 vs.11.0 days P value <0.001) respectively,and diet recovery was faster in coblation than conventional(6.2 vs. 9.2 days P value <0.001).This was statistically significant with p value <0.001.⁶⁸

CONCLUSION

Coblation method is relatively easy to perform, providing a bloodless field and minimal tissue damage. Coblation tonsillectomy is comparatively better than conventional as it takes less operative time and the intraoperative blood loss is less as bleeding can be controlled better than conventional method due to ablative property of wand. The postoperative pain scores and the time required to return to normal diet and activity are less than the conventional method.

REFERENCES

1. Wiatrak BJ, Woolley AL (2005) Pharyngitis and adenotonsillar disease. In: Cummings CW, Flint PW, Harker LA, Haughey BH, Richardson MA, Robbins KT (eds) Cummings otolaryngology; head and neck surgery, 4th edn. Elsevier, Mosby, Baltimore, pp 4135–4165.
2. Vaishali A Patel., *et al.* “Coblation Versus Conventional Tonsillectomy: Our Institutional Experience”. *Acta Scientific Otolaryngology* 2.5 (2020):25-28.
3. Raut V, Bhat N, Kinsella J, Toner JG, Sinnathuray AR, Stevenson M. Bipolar scissors versus cold dissection tonsillectomy: a prospective, randomized, multi-unit study. *Laryngoscope*. 2001;111(12):2178–82.
4. Temple RH and Timms MS. “Paediatric coblation tonsillectomy”. *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology* 61.3 (2001): 195-198.
5. “COBLATION Plasma Technology - ENT”. Smith and Nephew US Professional (2016).
6. Belloso A., *et al.* “Coblation tonsillectomy versus dissection tonsillectomy: postoperative hemorrhage”. *Laryngoscope* 113.11 (2003): 2010-2013.
7. Plant RL. “Radiofrequency treatment of tonsillar hypertrophy”. *Laryngoscope* 112.8 (2002): 20-22.7.
8. Bluestone and Stoel's paediatric otorhinolaryngology, 5th edition.
9. Pang YT (1995) Paediatric tonsillectomy: bipolar electrodissection and dissection/snare compared. *J Laryngol Otol* 109(8):733–736.
10. Chang KW. Randomized controlled trial of coblation versus electrocautery tonsillectomy. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2005;132.
11. Stoker KE, Don DM, Kang DR, *et al.* Pediatric total tonsillectomy using coblation compared to conventional electrosurgery: a prospective, controlled, single-blind study. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2004;130:666 – 675.

12.Omrani M, Barati B, Omidifar N, Okhovvat AR, Hashemi SA. Coblation versus traditional tonsillectomy: A double blind randomized controlled trial. J Res Med Sci. 2012 Jan;17(1):45-50.

13.Shapiro NL, Bhattacharyya N. Cold Dissection Versus Coblation-assisted adenotonsillectomy in children.Laryngoscope. 2007; 117(3): 406-410.

14.Muthubabu K, Rekha A, Thejas SR, Vinayak R, Srinivasan MK, Alagammai S, Thushita Nivasini S, Gayathri S. Tonsillectomy by Cold Dissection and Coblation Techniques: A Prospective Comparative Study. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2019 Oct;71(Suppl 1):665-670.

15.El-Taher M, Aref Z. Coblation Versus Conventional Tonsillectomy: A Double Blind Randomized Controlled Trial. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2019 Oct;71(Suppl 1):172-175.

16.Sasindran, V. , Mathew, N. , Shabna, A. and Harikrishan, B. (2019) Comparison of Coblation Tonsillectomy vs Dissection Tonsillectomy. *International Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery*, **8**, 49-60.

17.Vyas S, SharmaP, SharmaN, MakwanaA, GoyalVP.Coblation vs dissection tonsillectomy: a prospective randomized study comparing surgicaland clinical outcomes. IntJ Otorhinolaryngol Head Neck Surg 2019;5:306-9.

18.KarathiaNM, KansaraAH.Comparison of tonsillectomy by coblation and tonsillectomy by conventional method.Int J Otorhinolaryngol Head Neck Surg2020;6:923-8.

19.Lou Z, Lou Z, Lv T, Chen Z. A prospective, randomized, single-blind study comparing coblation and monopolar extracapsular tonsillectomy.Laryngoscope Investig Otolaryngol. 2022 Mar 29;7(3):707-714.

20.Chaudhary K, Singh V, Yadav R, Chaudhary AK, Kumar R, Gupta DK, Verma JK. Comparative Study of Complications Associated with Coblation Versus Conventional Tonsillectomy. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2023 Dec;75(4):2870-2877.

21.Scott Brown –Textbook of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, 8th Edition.

22.Philpott CM, Wild DC, Mehta D, Daniel M, Banerjee AR. A double-blinded randomized controlled trial of coblation versus conventional dissection tonsillectomy

on post-operative symptoms. *Clinical Otolaryngology : Official Journal of ENT-UK ; Official Journal of Netherlands Society for Oto-rhino-laryngology & Cervico-facial Surgery*. 2005 Apr;30(2):143-148.

23. Feery BJ, Forsell P, Gulasekharam M. Streptococcal sore throat in general practice: A controlled study. *Med J Aust* 1976; 1: 989–91.

24. Powell J, Wilson JA. An evidence-based review of peritonsillar abscess. *Clin Otolaryngol* 2012;37: 136–45.

25. Sprinkle PM, Veltri RW. The tonsils and adenoids. *Clinical Otolaryngology* 1977; 2: 153–67.

26. Little P, Williamson I, Warner S, et al. Open randomised trial of prescribing strategies in managing sore throat. *BMJ* 1997; 314: 722– 7.

27. Brook I. Microbiology and management of peritonsillar, retropharyngeal and parapharyngeal abscesses. *J Oral Maxillofacial Surgery* 2004; 62: 1545–50.

28. Young, B., Woodford, P., & O’Dowd, G. (2013). *Wheater’s functional histology* (6th ed.). Churchill Livingstone. 2013;216f

29. RonB Mitchell Clinical practice guideline: Tonsillectomy in children updates 2011.

30. Surow JB, Handler SD, Telian SA, et al. Bacteriology of tonsil surface and core in children. *Laryngoscope* 1989; 99: 261–6.

31. Brook I, Gober AE. Increased recovery of *Moraxella catarrhalis* and *Haemophilus influenzae* in association with group A beta-haemolytic streptococci in healthy children and those with pharyngo- tonsillitis. *J Med Microbiol* 2006; 55: 989–92.

32. Cherry JD. Pharyngitis (pharyngitis, tonsillitis, tonsillo-pharyngitis, and nasopharyngitis). In: Feigin RD et al., eds. *Textbook of Pediatric Infectious Diseases*. 5th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Saunders; 2004:161–170.

33. Nallasivam, A Comparative study of coblation versus conventional tonsillectomy, 2017 IOSR 10.9790.

34. Brook I, Foote PA. Isolation of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from the surface and core of tonsils in children. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol* 2006; 70: 2099–102.
35. Kaygusuz I, Alpay HC, Gödekmerdan A, et al. Evaluation of long-term impacts of tonsillectomy on immune functions of children: a follow up study. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol* 2009; 73: 445–9.
36. Singh Amandeep, Tuli BS, Tuli Isha Preet, Tuli Navneet Kaur, et al. *Textbook of Ear, Nose and Throat* (2nd ed). 2013; page 7
37. Friedman M, Hwang MS. Brodsky and Friedman Scales and Clinical Tonsil Size Grading in Children. *JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2015;141(10):947–948.
38. Mitchell RB, Archer SM, Ishman SL, et al (2019) Clinical practice guideline: tonsillectomy in children (update). *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 160(1_ suppl):S1-S42.
39. Verma R, Verma RR, Verma RR (2017) Tonsillectomy-comparative study of various techniques and changing trend. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 69(4):549–558.
40. Paradise JL, Bluestone CD, Bachman RZ, et al. History of recurrent sore throat as an indication for tonsillectomy. Predictive limitations of histories that are undocumented. *N Engl J Med*. 1978;298:409–413.
41. Al-Hussaini A, Owens D, Tomkinson A. Health costs and consequences: have UK national guidelines had any effect on tonsillectomy rates and hospital admissions for tonsillitis? *Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol* 2013; 270: 1959–65.
42. Lorraine A McSweeney, Janet A Wilson, Scott Wilkes, Catherine A Haighton, Is Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network guidance for GP management of tonsillitis suitable? A qualitative study, *Family Practice*, Volume 35, Issue 5, October 2018, Pages 633–637.
43. Paradise J L, Bluestone CD, et al 2001. Efficacy of tonsillectomy for recurrent throat infection in severely affected children. 113-27.
44. Alexandria et al american academy of otolaryngology head and neck surgery 1995 94.

45. Mitchell RB, Archer SM, Ishman SL, Rosenfeld RM, Coles S, Finestone SA, Friedman NR, Giordano T, Hildrew DM, Kim TW, Lloyd RM, Parikh SR, Shulman ST, Walner DL, Walsh SA, Nnacheta LC. Clinical Practice Guideline: Tonsillectomy in Children (Update). *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2019 Feb;160(1_suppl):S1- S42.
46. ArthroCare Corporation Coblator Plasma Surgery System. Entec, Sunnyvale, CA. (2000).
47. Thiagarajan, Balasubramanian. (2014). Coblation an overview. *Otolaryngology Online Journal.* 4. 1-6.
48. Benninger MS. Laser surgery for nodules and other benign laryngeal lesions. *Curr Opin Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2009 Dec;17(6):440-4.
49. J. WOLOSZKO et al., ArthroCare Corp., Sunnyvale, CA 94086, United States. *Lasers in surgery : advanced characterization, therapeutics, and systems X (San Jose CA, 22-23, 25 January 2000) SPIE.* 2000 Jan;25:306-316.
50. Prasad KC, Prasad SC. Assessment of Operative Blood Loss and the Factors Affecting it in Tonsillectomy and Adenotonsillectomy. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2011 Oct;63(4):343-8.
51. Wong DL, Hockenberry-Eaton M, Wilson D, Winkelstein ML, Schwartz P: *Wong's Essentials of Pediatric Nursing*, 6/e, St. Louis, 2001, P. 1301.
52. Coté, Charles J.; Jerrold Lerman; I. David Todres (2009). *A practice of anesthesia for infants and children.* Elsevier Health Sciences. p. 940.
53. Drendel, AL; Kelly, BT; Ali, S (August 2011). "Pain assessment for children: overcoming challenges and optimizing care". *Pediatric Emergency Care.* 27 (8): 773–81.
54. Myatt HM and Myatt RA. "The Development of a Pediatric Quality of Life Questionnaire to Measure Post-operative Pain Following Tonsillectomy". *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology* 44.2 (1998): 115-123.
55. Lowe D, van der Meulen J, Cromwell D, Lewsey J, Copley L, Browne J, et al. Key messages from the National Prospective Tonsillectomy Audit. *Laryngoscope.* 2007;117(4):717–24.
56. Pinder DK, Wilson H, Hilton MP. Dissection versus diathermy for tonsillectomy. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2011;(3):CD002211.

57. Al-Shehri AMS, Alenzi HLS, Ali Mohammed YM, Musleh A, Bharti RK, Saeed Munshet AM. Cauterization tonsillectomy as compared to traditional tonsillectomy technique. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2020 Aug 25;9(8):3981-3985.
58. Timms MS, Temple RH. Coblation tonsillectomy: a double blind randomized controlled study. *J Laryngol Otol*. 2002;116(6):450–2.
59. Tan AK, Hsu PP, Eng SP, Ng YH, Lu PK, Tan SM, et al. Coblation vs electrocautery tonsillectomy: postoperative recovery in adults. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2006;135(5):699–703.
60. National Institute For Clinical Excellence. Interventional Procedure Overview of Coblation Tonsillectomy. London: Anonymous; 2002.
61. Polites N, Joniau S, Wabnitz D, Fassina R, Smythe C, Varley P, et al. Postoperative pain following coblation tonsillectomy: randomized clinical trial. *ANZ J Surg*. 2006;76(4):226–9.
62. Burton MJ, Doree C. Coblation versus other surgical techniques for tonsillectomy. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2007;(3):CD004619.
63. Noon AP, Hargreaves S. Increased postoperative haemorrhage seen in adult coblation tonsillectomy. *J Laryngol Otol*. 2003;117(9):704–6.
64. Nelson J, Varghese N, Joseph AC, Menon AG, Antony R. A comparative study of conventional cold dissection and coblation method of tonsillectomy. *Int J Adv Med Health Res* 2023;10:17-21.
65. Hong SM, Cho JG, Chae SW, Lee HM, Woo JS. Coblation vs. Electrocautery Tonsillectomy: A Prospective Randomized Study Comparing Clinical Outcomes in Adolescents and Adults. *Clin Exp Otorhinolaryngol*. 2013 Jun;6(2):90-3.
66. Sheet MS, Al-Banna AF, Emanuel ES, Mohammed AA, Alnori H. Coblation Versus Cold Dissection Tonsillectomy: A Comparative Study. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2022 Dec;74(Suppl 3):5706-5711.
67. Jat SL, Jat KS, Sehra R, Sharma MP, Sharma A. Traditional and Coblation Tonsillectomy in Pediatrics Population: A Comparative Study. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2022 Dec;74(Suppl 3):6414-6421.

68.Omrani M, Barati B, Omidifar N, Okhovvat AR, Hashemi SA. Coblation versus traditional tonsillectomy: A double blind randomized controlled trial. *J Res Med Sci*. 2012 Jan;17(1):45-50.

69.Nallasivam, Dr & Sivakumar, Dr.M.. (2017). A comparative study of coblation versus conventional tonsillectomy.. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*. 16. 102-107.

70.Stefan Konsulov, Spas Konsulov, Karen Dzhambazov, Petar Kopanov. Comparison Between Coblation Assisted Tonsillectomy Versus Conventional Tonsillectomy Regarding the Postoperative Pain and Bleeding. *International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*. Vol. 3, No. 1, 2017, pp. 1-5.

71.Divi V, Benninger M. Postoperative tonsillectomy bleed: coblation versus noncoblation. *Laryngoscope*. 2005 Jan;115(1):31-3.

72.Rakesh S, Anand TS, Payal G, Pranjali K. A Prospective, Randomized, Double-Blind Study of Coblation versus Dissection Tonsillectomy in Adult Patients. *Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2012 Sep;64(3):290-4.

73.Dr Saadhya shukla, et. al. "Comparative study of surgical outcome of coblation versus conventional tonsillectomy." *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences (IOSR-JDMS)*,21(06), 2022, pp. 11-19.

ANNEXURES I

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

BLDE
(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)
Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)
The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA
BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 709/2022-23 30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COBLATION VS CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. Radhika Krishnan

NAME OF THE GUIDE: Dr. H. T. Lathadevi, Professor Dept. of ENT.

Dr.Santoshkumar Jeevanagi
Chairperson
IEC-SBMPMC,
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr.Akram A. Naikawadi
Member Secretary
IEC-SBMPMC,
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization.

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.
BLDE (DU): Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263303, Website: www.bldedu.ac.in, E-mail: office@bldedu.ac.in
College: Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263019, E-mail: bmpmc.principal@bldedu.ac.in

ANNEXURE -11

PROFORMA

NAME:

CASE NO:

AGE:

UHID NO:

SEX:

DOA:

RELIGION:

DOS:

OCCUPATION:

DOD:

SCHEME OF CASE TAKING

RESIDENCE:

CHIEF COMPLAINTS:

HISTORY OF PRESENTING ILLNESS:

PAST HISTORY:

ALLERGY

BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

PREVIOUS THROAT SURGERY

IRRADIATION

HYPERTENSION

PULMONARY TB

DIABETES

PRESENT	ABSENT

PERSONAL HISTORY:

SMOKING

ALCOHOLISM

DIET

BOWEL AND BLADDER HABITS

PRESENT	ABSENT

FAMILY HISTORY:

PRESENT	ABSENT

GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

PALLOR

ICTERUS

CYANOSIS

CLUBBING

LYMPHADENOPATHY

OEDEMA

PRESENT	ABSENT

VITALS

PR:

BP:

RR:

TEMP:

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

RESPIRATORY SYSTEM

CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

GASTROINTESTINAL SYSTEM

LOCAL EXAMINATION OF ORALCAVITY:

MOUTH OPENING

ORAL HYGIENE :

LIPS:

TEETH:

TONGUE:

GUM:

GBS:

BUCCAL MUCOSA:

RMT:

FLOOR OF MOUTH:

PALATE:

PRESENT	ABSENT

OROPHARYNX

ANTERIOR PILLAR:

TONSILLAR FOSSA:

UVULA;

PPW:

POSTERIOR PILLAR :

PRESENT	ABSENT

L/E OF NECK:

LYMPHADENOPATHY

JUGULODIGASTRIC LYMPH NODES

PRESENT	ABSENT

NOSE (ANTERIOR RHINOSCOPY)

NASAL CAVITY:

NASAL SEPTUM:

NASAL MUCOSA:

TURBINATES:

PRESENT	ABSENT

EAR PINNA

PRE AURICULAR AREA

POST AURICULAR AREA

EAC

TM

PRESENT	ABSENT

INVESTIGATION:

COMPLETE BLOOD COUNT

BT, CT

URINE EXAMINATION

HIV RAPID, HBS AG SPOT & HCV SPOT TEST

RBS, BLOOD UREA, SERUM CREATININE

CHEST XRAY, ECG

PRESENT	ABSENT

FINAL DIAGNOSIS:
OPERATIVE DATA

PREOPERATIVE:

INJ AMOXICILLIN CLAVULANIC ACID GIVEN PREOPERATIVELY TO ALL PATIENTS .

TYPE OF TONSILLECTOMY OPERATION DONE :

- COBLATION
- DISSECTION & SNARE

INTRAOPERATIVE FINDINGS:

TIME TAKEN FOR SURGERY:

1)INSERTION OF BOYLE DAVIS MOUTH GAG -

2)REMOVAL OF BOYLE DAVIS MOUTH GAG -

TIME TAKEN IN MINUTES:

BLOOD LOSS DURING SURGERY:

TOTAL FLUID IN SUCTION JAR:

FLUID USED FOR PROCEDURE:

NUMBER OF PADS SOAKED :

PRIMARY HAEMORRHAGE:

NUMBER OF LIGATURES DONE

POST OPERATIVE FINDINGS FOR 10 DAYS:

POSTOPERATIVE PAIN SCALE:

TIME REQUIRED TO RETURN TO NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY

PATIENT'S RETURN TO NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY:

POSTOPERATIVE FOLLOW UP :10 DAYS

REACTIONARY HEMORRHAGE –

AMOUNT OF BLOOD LOSS:

STEPS TAKEN TO CONTROL /TREAT:

SECONDARY HEMORRHAGE -

AMOUNT OF BLOOD LOSS

STEPS TAKEN TO CONTROL /TREAT

POD-1

POD -5

POD-10

Chang and Myatt to evaluate patients, return to normal diet and activity and pain level

	POD-1	POD-5	POD-10
Have your child been drinking? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗು ಕುಡಿದಿದೆಯೇ?			
Have your child been eating? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗು ತಿನ್ನುತ್ತಿದೆಯೇ?			
What kind of foods have your child been eating? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗು ಯಾವ ರೀತಿಯ ಆಹಾರವನ್ನು ತಿನ್ನುತ್ತಿದೆ?			
Have your child been talking? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗು ಮಾತನಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆಯೇ?			
Have your child been active? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗು ಸಕ್ರಿಯವಾಗಿದೆಯೇ?			
How was your child's mood? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗುವಿನ ಮನಸ್ಥಿತಿ ಹೇಗಿತ್ತು?			
Have your child been playing? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗು ಆಟವಾಡುತ್ತಿದೆಯೇ?			
Did your child miss school/daycare today? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಮಗು ಇಂದು ಶಾಲೆ/ ಡೇಕೇರ್ ಅನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಂಡಿದೆಯೇ?			
Did you have to miss work today? ನೀವು ಇಂದು ಕೆಲಸವನ್ನು ಕಳೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕೇ?			
Did you complete your planned activities and errands for today? ನಿಮ್ಮ ಯೋಜನೆಯನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸಿದ್ದೀರಾ ಇಂದಿನ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳು?			

ANNEXURE –III

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

BLDE (deemed to be university)

**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND
RESEARCH CENTRE ,VIJAYAPURA, 586103.**

TITLE OF THE PROJECT

**“A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COBLATION VS
CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY”**

PG STUDENT

Dr. RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN
DEPARTMENT OF
OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPUR, KARNATAKA– 586103

PG GUIDE

Dr.H.T.LATHADEVI
DEPARTMENT OF
OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPURA, KARNATAKA– 586103

All aspects of this consent form are explained to the patient in the language understood by him/her

1) PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed about this study. I have also been given a free choice of participation in this study.

2) PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this study.

3) RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

4) BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to improve survival of the patient and will bring about a better outcome.

5) PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this study.

6) RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

7) BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to improve survival of the patient and will bring about a better outcome.

8) CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of Hospital records and will be subject to the confidentiality and privacy regulation. Information of a sensitive personal nature will not be a part of the medical records, but will be stored in the investigator's research file and identified only by a code number. The code-key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate location. If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose, no name will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or videotapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photographs and videotapes and hear the audiotapes before giving this permission.

9) REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time. Dr.RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which

might influence my continued participation.

If during the study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

10) REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital. I also understand that DR.RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN may terminate my participation in the study after she has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or physical therapist, if this is appropriate.

11) INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits to the best of my ability in patient's own language.

Dr. RADHIKA R KRISHNAN

(Investigator)

Date

.STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT

I confirm that DR. RADHIKA.R.KRISHNAN has explained to me the purpose of the research, the study procedures that I will undergo, and the possible risks and discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my own language. I have read and understand this consent form. Therefore, I agree to consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

Participant / Guardian

Date

Witness to signature

Date

ANNEXURE IV

PLAGIARISM CHECK

iThenticate Similarity Report ID: oid:361863180402

PAPER NAME	AUTHOR
A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF COBLATION VS CONVENTIONAL TONSILLECTOMY	RADIKA KRISHNAN

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ANNEXURE V

KEY TO MASTERCHART

S. No	Serial Number
INTRA OP BLOOD LOSS	INTRAOPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS
POST OP BLOOD LOSS	POST OPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS
F	FEMALE
M	MALE
MIN	MINUTES
ML	MILIMETER

MASTER CHART

S.NO	NAME	AGE	SEX	UHID NO		OPERATIVE TIME IN SECONDS		POST OP BLOOD LOSS REACTIONARY	POST OP BLOOD LOSS SECONDARY	POST OPPAIN DAY 1	POST OPPAIN DAY 5	POST OPPAIN DAY 10	TIME REQUIRED TO RETURN TO NORMAL DIET AND ACTIVITY
1	HANAMANT TAMADADDI	15M		353846	COBLATION	29 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	3
2	PRUTHVIRAJ YELLAPPA HARIJAN	8M		244782	COBLATION	35 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	0	5
3	CHE TAN S WADI	7M		117037	COBLATION	22 MIN	56 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	6
4	SANA GOUS GOKAK	16F		266976	COBLATION	33 MIN	35 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	0	3
5	JYOTI MAHADEV HARURAGERI	14F		150052	COBLATION	26 MIN	70 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	0	3
6	GANESH ANAND KONDAGALI	9M		78369	COBLATION	25 MIN	67 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	4
7	SAVITA Y BULAVAGOL	29F		368616	COBLATION	30 MIN	47 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	4
8	RUHAN MANKANI	13F		227229	COBLATION	30 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	0	3
9	PANKAJ SHIRIKANTH JADHAV	10M		151155	COBLATION	34 MIN	55 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	4
10	JYOTHI SRINATH JADAV	35F		121271	COBLATION	20 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	3
11	PRIYANKA RAMESH GUNNAPUR	15F		300804	COBLATION	55 MIN	75 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	4
12	SEEMAIQABAL WADODAGI	23F		299219	COBLATION	30 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	4	7
13	MAHANTESH PATIL	17M		275569	COBLATION	42 MIN	44 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	0	3

14	SHABANA DOULSAB	9	F	259832	COBLATION	33 MIN	66 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	7
15	ALHYAZ YOUSUF USTAD	10	F	395906	COBLATION	28 MIN	50 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	5
16	SANIDHI MANDEWALE	44	F	397267	COBLATION	44 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	3
17	SUREKHA BASAVARAJ	45	F	395978	COBLATION	23 MIN	70 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	0	7

	BALLOLLI											
18	POOJA PARASURAM LAMANI	14F	167357	COBLATION	25 MIN	30 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	0	4
19	SANCHITA IKKALAKI	14F	167357	COBLATION	20 MIN	55 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	3
20	DAYANAND IRANNAKUMBAR	7M	267955	COBLATION	27 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	5
21	BHAGYASHR EEKUMBAR	17F	178983	COBLATION	30 MIN	49 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	5
22	SAWSATIK MAHANTESH HIDIKAL	10F	184074	COBLATION	20 MIN	50 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	3
23	PRASAD ASHOK DODOMANI	16M	52211	COBLATION	40 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	3
24	MALLAMMA LAXMAN KADIMANI	35F	136406	COBLATION	39 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	6
25	BASAVATRAY PRABHUGOU DA	14M	400343	COBLATION	22 MIN	44 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	0	6
26	SHRUTIKA RUNWAL	20F	382014	COBLATION	20 MIN	35 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	5
27	AKASH BHAGANNA PUJARI	9M	382014	COBLATION	35 MIN	50 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	5
28	NINGANAGOUDA BIRADAR	14M	356541	COBLATION	29 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	0	5
29	JANABAI PAWAR	24F	360085	COBLATION	32 MIN	65 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	4
30	MEGHA	13F	323884	COBLATION	27 MIN	50 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	0	5
31	AISHWARYA LAXMAN MEDEDAR	20F	122982	COBLATION	35 MIN	27 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	3
32	SUREKHA AMASIDDA BIRADAR	20F	119798	COBLATION	32 MIN	35 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	4	3
33	BORAMMA MUTTAPPA INDI	11F	119798	COBLATION	20 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	4

34	SHREEYA ADDODAGI	11F	153317	COBLATION	30 MIN	45 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	5
35	ASIF IMAMHUSSAIN JAKATI	23M	06073	COBLATION	36 MIN	74 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	5
36	PRATEEK PRALAHAD KANAMADI	9M	97308	COBLATION	27 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	0	3
37	MAHAMMADSALEM G AGANI	9M	91230	COBLATION	33 MIN	39 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	5
38	PALLAVI MANJUNATH SANGAPUR	5F	144881	COBLATION	20 MIN	45 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	4
39	PRUTHVIK AVAJI	4M	115153	COBLATION	30 MIN	67 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	4	3
40	AJAY	11M	85747	COBLATION	23 MIN	50 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	2	5
41	MEGHA L HOSUR	12F	395462	COBLATION	35 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	5
42	RAJESHWARI CHALAWADI	6F	395448	COBLATION	35 MIN	35 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	4
43	PRABUDDHA LINGADALLI	4M	433681	COBLATION	28 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	5
44	SUCHITRA MALLAPPA WADI	6F	355995	COBLATION	24 MIN	70 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	0	4
45	HARIPRASAD SHANKAR PUJARI	7M	375913	COBLATION	20 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	2	3
46	MASTER NEHAL	6M	134876	COBLATION	34 MIN	50 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	0	3
47	BHAGYASHREE	12F	107592	COBLATION	20 MIN	44 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	3
48	ATHARVA MANJUNATH	13M	123827	COBLATION	36 MIN	74 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	2	5
49	CHANDRIKA	28F	367332	COBLATION	22 MIN	56 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	0	5
50	SUSHANT BASANAGOUDA	15M	163530	COBLATION	28 MIN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	0	4
51	CHETANA	8F	159788	COBLATION	33 MIN	40 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	4	5
52	VILAS	15M	142353	COBLATION	20 MIN	55ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	6	2	4
53	FALAKNAZ	10F	122727	COBLATION	27 MIN	66ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	4

54	PRIYANKA	28F	163974	COBLATION	36 MIN	35ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	0	3
55	AKSHATA	16F	419050	COBLATION	40 IN	60 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	6	0	6
56	SANVI JALAPUR	7F	446076	CONVENTIONAL	49 MIN	75 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	4	10
57	BHAGYSHRI BULLAVGOL	8F	432588	CONVENTIONAL	52 MIN	80 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	8
58	RENUKA PARAMANNA MADAR	22F	445879	CONVENTIONAL	39 MIN	77 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	6	10
59	SAKASHI DUNDAPPA BAGALI	6F	21943	CONVENTIONAL	56 MIN	85 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	7
60	SALMA HOSATTI	16F	215040	CONVENTIONAL	90 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	4	9
61	LAXMI AMBALANUR	12F	210185	CONVENTIONAL	60 MIN	140 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	8
62	LAXMI MALAKANNA	31F	215367	CONVENTIONAL	50 MIN	76 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	8
63	KANYAKUMARI LAXMIKANTH	28F	194252	CONVENTIONAL	54 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	4	6
64	MAHADEVI RANCHAPPA	7F	102351	CONVENTIONAL	90 MIN	120 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	2	9
65	ADITYA ANIL PAWAR	12M	219932	CONVENTIONAL	50 MIN	84 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	7
66	SHIVAPPA MADAR	15M	219928	CONVENTIONAL	37 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	4	9
67	SINCHANNA P KHANDEKAR	8F	65592	CONVENTIONAL	40 MIN	130 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	10
68	ANAND SOMALU RATHOD	38M	95350	CONVENTIONAL	50 MIN	75 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	6
69	ASHA HAVALDAR	23F	326550	CONVENTIONAL	44 MIN	110 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	0	8
70	RAMESH NENAPPA KOLI	22M	65257	CONVENTIONAL	45 MIN	80 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	9
71	SHRUTI BHIM TALAWAR	11F	328059	CONVENTIONAL	60 MIN	100 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	6	10
72	SANJIVINI SHIVANAND BADOLE	16F	246768	CONVENTIONAL	80 MIN	85 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	4	7

73	BOURAMMA SEETARAM	9F	356002	CONVENTIONAL	46 MIN	97 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	6
74	NAGAMMA SHIVASHANKAR	50F	212555	CONVENTIONAL	50 MIN	69 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	7
75	NIHANTHA NAINEGALI	8F	167868	CONVENTIONAL	40 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	10
76	VIJAYLAXMI KUMBAR	9F	397068	CONVENTIONAL	29 MIN	75 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	4	10
77	MANOJ MALLIKARJUN	8M	151166	CONVENTIONAL	57 MIN	100 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	6
78	JAYASHREE SANTOSH NAVI	26F	279491	CONVENTIONAL	34 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	2	6
79	ANAND UPPAR	8M	299947	CONVENTIONAL	50 MIN	77 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	8
80	PRAVEEN BASAVARAJ CHIPPARAKATTI	13M	224358	CONVENTIONAL	67 MIN	77 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	5
81	DASTAGIRASAB KAJASAB MULLA	12M	258251	CONVENTIONAL	39 MIN	66 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	2	10
82	NILAMBIKA BASANNA RUDAGI	17F	428770	CONVENTIONAL	46 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	6	8
83	SAMARTH BABAR	9M	308373	CONVENTIONAL	60 MIN	80 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	10
84	BASANGOUDA BIRADAR	16M	166194	CONVENTIONAL	48 MIN	70 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	7
85	BHOOMIKA HARIJAN	17F	395413	CONVENTIONAL	74 MIN	80 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	4	9
86	VIKAS GURALINGAPPA KYADAGI	12M	324400	CONVENTIONAL	52 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	6	10
87	BANGARAPPA BABU DASAVANTH	23M	119807	CONVENTIONAL	57 MIN	76 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	5
88	SUJATHA KALLAPPA BATAGUNAKI	29F	129675	CONVENTIONAL	70 MIN	100 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	7
89	AKASH RUDARESH PUJARI	8M	123072	CONVENTIONAL	44 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	2	10
90	NANDITA BIRADAR	11F	127332	CONVENTIONAL	34 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	5

91	GURUDEVI BASAVRAJ MADANSHETTI	50F	387872	CONVENTIONAL	64 MIN	88 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	0	9
92	GAYATRI BHEEMASHANKAR SALIMATH	12F	21213	CONVENTIONAL	55 MIN	75 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	4	5
93	POORNIMA RAMESH DANDARAGI	13F	16942	CONVENTIONAL	47 MIN	95 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	4	10
94	MADHU G ALOOR	10M	23203	CONVENTIONAL	54 MIN	55 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	6	8
95	SAMARTH SHIVANAND HOSAMANI	9M	29949	CONVENTIONAL	57 MIN	110 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	10
96	VEERESH MAHANTESH BADIGAR	12M	39195	CONVENTIONAL	62 MIN	88 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	9
97	BHUMI LADAPPA POLARI	7F	42614	CONVENTIONAL	74 MIN	110 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	7
98	SHIVASHANKAR UPPALADINNI	6M	37924	CONVENTIONAL	40 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	2	10
99	GEETA RATHOD	36F	79861	CONVENTIONAL	50 MIN	80 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	2	9
100	SUVARNA DATTATREY SARAF	F	74203	CONVENTIONAL	65 MIN	75 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	6	10
101	BHAGYASHREE IRANNA NATIKAR	12F	107592	CONVENTIONAL	46 MIN	110 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	4	2	10
102	NEHAL SUBHASH SHIEEVANT	6M	140962	CONVENTIONAL	74 MIN	90 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	8	4	5
103	SWATI SURESH RATHOD	12F	429002	CONVENTIONAL	52 MIN	80 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	2	9
104	MANJUNATH MALLAPPA	28M	297350	CONVENTIONAL	60 MIN	90ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	6	8
105	AKSHATARAMACHA NDRA BALAGAV	16F	419050	CONVENTIONAL	44 MIN	88 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	8	4	7
106	RAGHAVENDRA	14M	160618	CONVENTIONAL	40 MIN	100ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	4	2	8
107	DANAMMA	14F	148111	CONVENTIONAL	57 MIN	120 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	6	6	7

108	SAMARTH	11	M	154339	CONVENTIONAL	55 MIN	55 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	8	6	6	8
109	BHAGYASHREE	12	F	107592	CONVENTIONAL	70 MIN	76 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	6	4	2	9
110	HUSANAPPA	23	M	039457	CONVENTIONAL	34 MIN	120 ML	ABSENT	ABSENT	10	8	4	5

